

Harmonised European Solutions for Testing Automation Road Transport

HEADSTART D.2.3 Assessment method for each of the use cases defined

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Glossary of terms

The HEADSTART's proposed glossary definition below are the most relevant terms in this report and mainly based HEADSTART deliverable D2.1 Common methodology for test, validation and certification [1], which can also be found on the HEADSTART website [2].

Term	Description
Communication (V2X)	<i>HEADSTART Key Enabling Technology (KET):</i> The passing of information from a vehicle to any entity that may affect the road user (e.g. vehicle) and vice versa
Concrete scenario	Parameterised model of the time sequence of scenes (logical scenario) which begins with an initial scene and defined point in time; the behaviour of the main actor (vehicle under test) is not further specified.
Cybersecurity	<i>HEADSTART Key Enabling Technology (KET):</i> Cybersecurity is the protection of connected systems including hardware, software and data from internal and external attacks carried by malicious entities with or without authorization.
Ego-vehicle	The Ego-vehicle is the automated vehicle from whose perspective the traffic situation is viewed. The data recorded by the ego-vehicle through its sensors describes the traffic situation from its perspective relative to its own condition.
Field testing	<i>HEADSTART test method:</i> All types of testing on public roads, with real elements (components, actors and environment), a real system and a real-world high level of variability.
Functional scenario	A functional scenario is a temporal sequence that describes one of the behaviours of a system during a specific use case, with a nominal scenario and alternative scenarios. It is described in a linguistic way or with a structured language. Functional scenarios are derived from driving functions. They are used to describe the use case at a high level (higher than logical and concrete scenarios).
Highway pilot	<i>HEADSTART use case:</i> The Conditional (SAE Level 3) or Highly Automated Driving (SAE Level 4) in non-congested conditions, on highways and other structurally separated roads, with a speed range of 30 km/h to 130 km/h
Logical scenario	Beginning with an initial scene, a model of the time sequence of scenes whose parameters are defined as ranges; at a defined point in time, the behaviour of the main actor (vehicle under test) is not further specified.
Minimum manoeuvre risk	A procedure aimed at reducing risks in traffic, which is automatically performed by the system when the driver does not respond to a transition demand (e.g. by reducing vehicle speed).
Platoon	A group of two or more automated cooperative vehicles in line, maintaining a close distance, typically such a distance to reduce fuel consumption by air drag, to increase traffic safety by use of additional ADAS-technology, and to improve traffic throughput because vehicles are driving closer together and take up less space on the road.
Positioning	<i>HEADSTART Key Enabling Technology (KET):</i> The acknowledgment of the spatial position of an asset in time, involving in autonomous vehicles relative positioning (for obstacle avoidance or precise guidance with respect to the road markings) and absolute positioning (for retrieving from the digital map the information needed for the navigation).
Proving ground testing	<i>HEADSTART test method:</i> All types of testing on proving ground with controlled environment and no virtual elements (components or actors and environment).

Safety	This is freedom from unacceptable or absence of unreasonable risk of physical injury or of damage to the health of people, either directly, or indirectly as a result of damage to property or to the environment.
Safety case	Argument that the safety requirements for an item are complete and satisfied by evidence compiled from work products of the safety activities during development.
Scenario	Abstraction and general description of a temporal and spatial traffic constellation without any specification of the parameters.
Scenario parameter	A scenario parameter is a value used to describe the characteristics of a scenario (e.g. minimum TTC, average speed, minimum distance and trajectory).
Scene	Snapshot that includes the moving and non-moving elements of the traffic environment, the self-representation of all actors and observers and the relations between those elements.
Test case	The set of conditions that are applied to test a function or system
Traffic jam chauffeur	<i>HEADSTART use case:</i> Conditional automated driving in traffic jams up to 60 km/h on motorways and motorway similar roads.
Truck platooning	<i>HEADSTART use case:</i> A group of two or more automated cooperative trucks drive together in a line, maintaining a close distance.
Type approval	The procedure whereby an approval authority certifies that a type of vehicle, system, component or separate technical unit satisfies the relevant administrative provisions and technical requirements.
Use case	Specification of a generalized field of application, possibly entailing the following information about the system: one or several scenarios; the functional range; the desired behaviour; and the system boundaries. Note 1 to entry: The use case description typically does not include a detailed list of all relevant scenarios for this use case. Instead a more abstract description of these scenarios is used.
Virtual testing	<i>HEADSTART test method:</i> All types of testing with only virtual elements (components, actors and environment)
XiL-based testing	<i>HEADSTART test method:</i> All types of testing where virtual and real elements (components, actors and/or environment) are combined.

List of abbreviations and acronyms

Abbreviation	Meaning
ACC	Adaptive Cruise Control
AD	Automated Driving
ADAS	Advanced Driver Assistance System
AEB	Autonomous Emergency Braking
ALKS	Automated Lane Keeping System
CAD	Connected and Automated Driving
CAV	Connected and Automated Vehicle
CC	Common Criteria
ECU	Electronic Control Unit
EMC	ElectroMagnetic Compatibility
EU	European Union
GNSS	Global Navigation Satellite System
GPS	Global Positioning System
HARA	hazard analysis and risk assessment
HD	High Definition
HEADSTART	Harmonised European Solutions for Testing Automated Road Transport
HMI	Human Machine Interface
I2V	Infrastructure to Vehicle
IMU	Inertial Measurement Unit
IT	Information Technology
KET	Key Enabling Technology
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
LIDAR	Light Detection And Ranging
NAP	National Admittance Procedure
OD	Operational Domain
ODD	Operational Design Domain
OEDR	Object and Event Detection and Response
OEM	Original Equipment Manufacturer
OSI	Open Simulation Interface
RSU	RoadSide Unit
SAE	Society of Automotive Engineers
SOTIF	Safety of the Intended Functionality
UN	United Nations
UNECE	United Nations Economic Commission for Europe
V2I	Vehicle to Infrastructure
V2V	Vehicle to Vehicle
V2X	Vehicle to Everything
VDLF	Vehicle Driving License Framework
VRU	Vulnerable Road User

VSSF	Vehicle Safety & Security Framework
VUT	Vehicle Under Test
XiL	X-in-the-Loop (Hardware and software in the loop)

Executive Summary

This deliverable presents the work done in HEADSTART work package 2: Task 2.4 “Definition of methodology for the targeted use cases”, with the 3 selected HEADSTART use cases: Highway pilot, Truck platooning and Traffic jam chauffeur.

Task 2.4 is the first step to the application and demonstration of the scenario-based HEADSTART safety assessment methodology, which is developed in HEADSTART work package 2. In HEADSTART WP3 “*Procedures, environments and tools*” the HEADSTART methodology is further detailed with procedures and tools. In WP4 “*Application and demonstration*” the HEADSTART methodology including these procedures and tools will be applied and demonstrated through the different HEADSTART use cases to show its potential, with task 2.4 as starting point.

This report describes some first insights of HEADSTART use case implications with respect to the HEADSTART methodology. It is not the objective to give the full picture yet, as this depends heavily on the specific Connected and Automated Vehicle (CAV) feature implementation and procedure and tools that are being developed in HEADSTART WP3. Some topics and challenges that are expected to rise with the specific HEADSTART use cases are touched upon. Special attention is given to the inclusion of HEADSTART Key Enabling Technologies (KETs): Communication (V2X) and Positioning as part of the method. The 3rd HEADSTART KET Cybersecurity is discussed in a separate section, as this is being treated in a different way than the other HEADSTART KETs, due to its different nature. The implications that rise from type approval side for the safety assessment are described, with special attention to the admittance and exemptions of CAVs for testing, demonstration or approval activities. Besides type approval authorities also the other two HEADSTART key user groups, OEMs & Tier1s and consumer testing, have been taken into account. For each of the 4 HEADSTART test methods (Field, Virtual, XiL-based and Proving ground testing) some implications are described upon considering the HEADSTART use cases or methodology in a more general way.

1 Introduction

1.1 The HEADSTART project in a nutshell

HEADSTART (Harmonised European Solutions for Testing Automated Road Transport) is a European project funded under Horizon 2020 Framework Programme within the call ART-01-2018 (the type: Research and Innovation action). HEADSTART is represented by the consortium of 17 partners that are top automotive manufacturers, suppliers, test labs and researcher institutes.

HEADSTART will define testing and validation procedures of Connected and Automated Driving (CAD) functions including:

- its key enabling technologies (i.e. Communication (V2X), Cybersecurity, Positioning) (KET)
- cross-links of all test instances such as simulation, proving grounds and real-world field tests
- safety and security performance validation according to the needs of key user groups (technology developers, consumer testing and type approval).

HEADSTART has 3 action pillars mapped with end users of the project results:

- Testing and validation (development): e.g. OEMs,
- Assessment - Consumer testing: e.g. Euro NCAP
- Certification (type approval): e.g. Type approval authorities & Technical services

FIGURE 1 HEADSTART OBJECTIVES

The five objectives of the HEADSTART project comprise:

- OBJECTIVE 1: IDENTIFY - Create a dynamic catalogue of existing methods, procedures and tools for testing, validation and certification considering multi-stakeholder requirements.
- OBJECTIVE 2: HARMONISE - Harmonisation of existing testing and validation approaches taking into account other industries and domains.
- OBJECTIVE 3: DEFINE & DEVELOP - Define and develop test, validation and certification methodologies and procedures for CAD building upon existing initiatives.
- OBJECTIVE 4: DEMONSTRATE - Demonstrate the developed methodologies, procedures and tools through the testing of relevant CAD use cases.
- OBJECTIVE 5: REACH CONSENSUS - Reach consensus by creating and managing an expert network of CAD testing to promote adoption of the project results considering multi-stakeholder needs.

WP7 Coordination and management - The main objective is to ensure the successful execution of the project through a professional and effective management and coordination, with the achievement of the project objectives. WP7 contains all the technical and administration related project management and will deal with all Data Management related issues.

WP8 Ethics requirements - The objective is to ensure compliance with the 'ethics requirements' set out in this work package.

1.2 Approach and structure of the deliverable

In this deliverable the activities within task 2.4 are presented, where the HEADSTART assessment method, developed in task 2.1, 2.2 and 2.3, is applied to the use cases selected by HEADSTART. This is the first step to the application and demonstration of the HEADSTART assessment method, which is done in more detail in WP3 and WP4 of HEADSTART. In this report some first insights will be described, like what the specific HEADSTART use cases (see 1.3: Highway pilot, Truck platooning & Traffic jam chauffeur) bring with respect to the HEADSTART assessment method. This report is not intended to give the full picture yet, as this depends heavily on the specific Connected and Automated Driving (CAD) feature implementation and procedure and tools that are being developed in HEADSTART WP3. Some topics and challenges that are expected to rise with the specific HEADSTART use cases will be introduced, with special focus on the HEADSTART KETs: Positioning, Communication (V2X) and Cybersecurity. Because of its specific nature Cybersecurity will be handled in a separate paragraph and is not further discussed on use case level. There is also a separate chapter dedicated to the implication the type approval has on the assessment method. Each of the 4 HEADSTART test methods (Field, Virtual, XiL-based and Proving ground testing) will be discussed individually.

The deliverable is structured as follows. After general introduction to the HEADSTART project (1.1) and this HEADSTART deliverable D2.3 (1.2), the selection of the HEADSTART use cases is briefly described in paragraph 1.3.

The HEADSTART assessment methodology described in chapter 2 is a combination of results from task 2.1, 2.2 and 2.3 reported in deliverables D2.1 [1] and D2.2 [3]. This contains the Overall methodology (2.1), Scenario selection and allocation (2.2) with a sub-paragraph on Scenario HEADSTART KET enrichment (2.2.1), Testing of scenarios (2.3) and Evaluation of test results (2.4). Special attention is paid to HEADSTART Key Enabling Technology Cybersecurity in paragraph 2.5 and the Methodology implications related to type approval in paragraph 2.6.

After that in chapter 0 the HEADSTART methodology is applied to 3 HEADSTART use cases separately in 3.1 Highway pilot, 3.2 Truck platooning and 3.3 Traffic jam chauffeur.

In chapter 4 the feasibility of the different test methods (4.1 Field testing, 4.2 Virtual testing, 4.3 XiL-based testing, 4.4 Proving ground testing) is described taking especially the 3 HEADSTART use cases into account.

Finally, in chapter 5, a conclusion is drawn and implications are discussed.

1.3 Selected HEADSTART use cases

Within HEADSTART task 1.4 a first selection of Connected and Automated Driving (CAD) scenarios was made as documented in deliverable D1.4 [4].

Based on the user needs identified at that stage in the project, and on the premise that all aspects are equally important, it seems reasonable to focus our efforts on the following use cases:

- Highway pilot
- Truck platooning
- Valet parking
- Traffic jam chauffeur
- Urban automated shuttle

Within HEADSTART a dedicated task force was created to evaluate which use cases will be used within HEADSTART in more detail to demonstrate the HEADSTART assessment method. One of the main considerations and challenges is the availability of so-called 'linked projects' of collaboration partners that could facilitate the application and demonstration of the HEADSTART assessment method. Furthermore, this was combined with the requirement that the selected use cases (and 'linked projects') should be capable of covering:

- HEADSTART KETs (Positioning, Communication (V2X), Cybersecurity)
- test methods (Field testing, Virtual testing, XiL-based testing, Proving ground testing)
- availability of scenarios
- HEADSTART key user groups (OEMs and Tier1s, Type approval authorities, Consumer testing)

Based on these requirements, 3 use cases have been selected that will be discussed and demonstrated in detail in this report and the remainder of the HEADSTART project:

- a) Highway pilot
- b) Truck platooning
- c) Traffic jam chauffeur

2 Assessment methodology

2.1 Overall methodology

In this chapter an overview on the overall methodology is given, based on the results of deliverable D2.1 [1] and D2.2 [3] of the HEADSTART project. In the following chapters the main building blocks are described in further detail. This is helpful to get an understanding of the methodology before referencing and adapting it to specific use cases.

A coarse overview is given in Figure 2. The general idea is to abstract the real-world traffic into scenarios. Thus, an analysis of these scenarios is possible and relevant scenarios can be selected. To extract scenarios from real-world data, different steps are necessary, as displayed in Figure 2 in “Database + Mechanics”. Another important input to the completeness of relevant scenarios comes from experts and constructed scenarios, since real-world input data might not be sufficient at all times. Output of the database is logical scenarios with their respective parameter distributions and exposure calculations.

There are existing scenario databases like PEGASUS, StreetWise or MOOVE from different initiatives, which will be utilized in the HEADSTART methodology application and demonstration. HEADSTART will not implement its own database.

The scenario selection and parameter variation process includes the selection of relevant scenarios for the specific driving function and the use case. Moreover, a test case is compiled by fixing the parameters within the variation and creating testable scenarios. Therefore, the selection also needs to analyse already performed tests and their respective evaluation.

After the selection, the scenarios need to be allocated among different testing capabilities. Especially, the simulation is an important component when it comes to testing, as the number of tests that can be feasibly performed is huge compared to proving ground testing. For more detailed and realistic analysis real components are necessary. Therefore, the testing will be executed on proving grounds. XiL-based testing is a combination of both virtual and real components. This enables the possibility to combine the ease of virtual tests with the realism of proving ground components. Especially, safety critical interactions between vehicles and VRUs or pedestrians are hardly testable on proving grounds without sophisticated robot platforms.

A special part within the methodology is reserved for Field testing. Due to the fact that specific driving scenarios can hardly be staged in the field, traditional scenario based testing is not applicable. In the HEADSTART methodology, Field testing is considered when testing KET phenomena. Especially, infrastructure based phenomena like multipath propagation or occlusions for communication signals can be found and tested quite well in real-world field tests. Thus, the existing infrastructure is taken into account and thereby scenarios related solely on KETs, with focus on Communication (V2X), are created and afterwards tested in that specific field.

Finally, testing results need to be evaluated with respect to pass/fail criteria, human performance, the use case and the driving function. Based on this evaluation a statement can be composed. Moreover, the results become input to further improve the different steps of the methodology. For example, the recorded test data can be fed back into the database, to increase completeness of scenarios, and results can be used to select relevant (parameter values of) use cases that are critical to the system under test.

FIGURE 2 OVERVIEW ON THE OVERALL METHODOLOGY OF THE HEADSTART PROJECT

2.2 Scenario selection and allocation

Selection process

The process for the selection of relevant scenarios is divided into two parts. First, all relevant logical scenarios based on functional requirements are filtered (see “Relevant Scenarios” block in Figure 3). The defined functional requirements of a driving function should at least consist of the Operational Design Domain (ODD), the Object and Event Detection and Response (OEDR) and the tactical manoeuvre behaviour. The Key Enabling Technologies (KETs) can either be categorized in a separated manner or integrated with the overall functional requirements. With these requirements a query can be created and sent to the scenario database.

As of right now, the scenario database is understood as a collection of logical scenarios. This includes all the necessary parameters (with their distributions) of all the defined scenario layers [1] [3]. This leads to some unclarity in defining the necessary query for the database, especially with too generic functional requirements. It is difficult to filter out from the scenario database, as the definition of the ODD (and the OEDR) does only partly match with the information given by the scenario layers of the logical scenario description. In the future, it is therefore expected to extend the definition of not only the ODD (and the general functional requirements needed from the driving function under test) but also the scenario database with additional meta data, to ensure better defined queries. One potential concrete solution could be to use the same tags, both in the scenarios, as well as in the functional description of the driving function. Further progress in reducing this issue is expected to happen in the proposed standardization projects ASAM OpenODD [5] and OpenLABEL [6].

The just described problem is especially imminent for each of the parameter distributions of the potential logical scenarios. Well defined functional requirements should lead to a query for the scenario database which is able to not only filter the relevant scenarios, but also limit the parameter values to the relevant range.

There is also a possibility to add additional scenarios to the filtered relevant scenarios from the scenario database. This is necessary if not all basic capabilities are tested (based on the functional requirements of the driving function). Finally, it is also intended that feedback from the evaluation process can be considered in this step as

well. This could mean that scenarios, which failed according to the respective pass/fail criteria, are evaluated once again (leading to potential changes in the test methods and/or the allocation of the scenario or with more refined parameter ranges).

After these initial steps, all the relevant logical scenarios, including their respective parameter distributions, are gathered. The next main step is to define the relevance of the parameters and combine them to concrete scenarios. First, for all parameters the relevance is assessed based on the probability distributions. Secondly, the parameters are combined, taking potential parameter constraints and relations into account. In addition, potential prohibited parameter combinations due to given constraints need to be considered as well. This can be seen in Figure 3, showing a logical scenario “follow” based on Scenarios for Development, Test and Validation of Automated Vehicles [7]. This leads then to concrete scenarios, which, in the next step of the overall methodology, are allocated to a specific test method.

FIGURE 3 STRUCTURE OF THE SCENARIO SELECTION PROCESS

Allocation Process

Each test method (Proving ground, XiL-based and Virtual testing) has its own capabilities and restrictions. Since they are fixed for a specific use case, it makes sense to define them to ensure a correct allocation of the scenarios. In addition, the logical scenarios (including parameters) are needed for the allocation decision (see Figure 4).

Capabilities can be divided into the categories “Sensor”, “Environment” and “Vehicle Dynamics”. These three categories can be represented by simulation models or the real world. This framework provides a possibility to categorize every possible test method in terms of its capabilities and is much needed for the allocation of the scenarios.

FIGURE 4 INPUT INFORMATION FOR THE ALLOCATION PROCESS

The scenario allocation process can be seen in Figure 5. After defining the capabilities for each test method, these capabilities will be matched with each logical scenario.

For every test method, the first step is to match the capabilities with the current logical scenario. This includes checking if all the elements needed for scenario execution, on a logical scenario level, are available (in case of Proving ground and XiL-based testing) and if the required model fidelity can be achieved (in case of XiL-based and Virtual testing). For XiL-based and Proving ground testing the second step is to match the capabilities with the actual parameter ranges of the parameters defined for every layer in the logical scenario.

At the end of the process, the requirements and capabilities will indicate which test methods can be used. In the best case all three methods fulfil the requirements, which leads to a “best fit” and therefore the strongest argument in terms of a safety case (ISO 26262 [8]). The three other possible test method combinations have increasing restrictions regarding the safety argument (ISO 26262 [8]) (from left to right in Figure 5). If for some reason the “best fit” is necessary (this could depend on the target group executing this process) the minimum requirements for achieving this could be transferred back to the required capabilities of the test methods.

Test method combinations without the usage of Virtual testing are possible but discouraged, as the other test methods have very high difficulties to fulfil the needed statistical test coverage in a cost effective way.

Test method combinations without the usage of the proving ground are possible, but the verification of the models used in Virtual and XiL-based testing need to rely on either the simple basic scenarios or other similar logical scenarios .

At the end of the just described process, the test capabilities of each test method are defined and the concrete scenarios (derived from the current logical scenario) can be allocated based on that. After this is done, the process gets repeated once again for the next logical scenario (and so on).

The above process describes what *possible test methods* are available. However, due to time and budget constraints and for efficiency reasons, the final selection of the test method may not be the ‘best fit’ from a technical perspective.

FIGURE 5 OVERVIEW OF THE SCENARIO ALLOCATION PROCESS

2.2.1 Scenario HEADSTART KET enrichment

The inclusion of the HEADSTART selected KETs: Positioning, Communication (V2X) and Cybersecurity in the selected relevant scenarios and the generation of specific parameters matching the situation described in the logical scenario is not an easy task for several reasons:

- (i) Most existing scenario descriptions from large databases/projects do not include the required HEADSTART KET information, and as a consequence, no consolidated language/format has been devised to include them
- (ii) Tools for test methods, in particular Virtual testing, do not integrate KET-related simulation capabilities, which might need to be either simplified or indirectly added by means of their consequences (e.g. noise on perceived object locations due to noise in positioning)
- (iii) KETs, like Positioning and Communication (V2X), are not generally independent from each other, and also have an impact on other scenario characteristics.
- (iv) Cybersecurity KET is even more difficult to integrate, since it is rather contextually regarded and may affect multiple elements including communication and/or positioning parameters, mixing them in a unified way.

The inclusion of HEADSTART selected KETs is directly linked to the scenario selected for testing and validation, the impact of those KETs are not independent to the situation. The Positioning or Communication (V2X) impact in a dense traffic area, urban canyon or highway is not the same. Therefore, it is important to analyze which is the situation described in the selected relevant scenario to perform the first analysis on how each HEADSTART KET might affect the ego-vehicle function. This analysis will result on a logical individual KET layer definition, where for a specific logical scenario the potential distribution of the relevant parameters for that situation are specified. The specific parameter selection and the potential parameter value distribution will be constrained by the specific functional scenario. In this approach the Cybersecurity KET is going to be treated separately since its actuation and thus impact is much more complex and may affect various modules and elements at the same time.

Once the relevant parameter distribution for each KET has been defined the generation of concrete layers for enriching the scenario description can be generated. However, due to the nature of the KETs there are some restrictions when deploying those layers. Depending on the parameter or effect that needs to be generated there

are limitations in both simulation and real world. Therefore, some specific concrete effects might only be tested either in real world or in simulation.

Figure 6 shows step by step the process.

FIGURE 6 HEADSTART KETs PARAMETER SELECTION FOR A LOGICAL SCENARIO

There exists no database containing HEADSTART KET information to be applied to specific scenarios nor a format definition to generate such database. In consequence, HEADSTART project will propose and generate some reduced dataset with KET related information for the three HEADSTART use cases: Highway pilot, Truck platooning and Traffic jam chauffeur. The data format will also be defined within the HEADSTART project where a format compatible with OpenSCENARIO [9] will be proposed for the sake of compatibility and potential standardisation of the language used to extend the scenarios with “shared digital information”. This could be done in an additional 6th layer to the described layer definitions from HEADSTART deliverables D2.1 [1] and D2.2 [3].

HEADSTART KETs: parameter selection

This section presents an insight of the approach that should be used to select HEADSTART KETs parameter for a specific Use Case. For the sake of clarity, the Highway pilot use case has been selected. This is not meant to be an exhaustive analysis; more details will be provided in WP3 and WP4.

HEADSTART KETs (Positioning, Communication (V2X), Cybersecurity) influence the system in multiple ways:

- The pilot is enabled on specific roads (for instance it is not allowed in urban roads), so global positioning must be considered since it can be used directly to enable the pilot;
- Some implementations of the highway pilot functionality may include communication with other vehicles and/or the infrastructure;
- Cyberattacks can modify positioning and v2x information.

Therefore, in the definition of the logical scenarios, and specifically of the “shared digital information” of the scenario model, KET parameters must be included.

1. Operational Design Domain analysis

It should be noted that the Highway pilot use case will evolve based on the technology availability and the willingness of the OEM to address a specific SAE J3016 Autonomous Driving Automation Level [10].

- SAE Level 2 highway pilot functionality: the AD function performs both longitudinal and lateral motion control but the driver is supposed to monitor the system and promptly react when necessary. This functionality is available in most advanced vehicles in the market.
 - Positioning: Only relative position is required as the driver is responsible of the route selection. The vehicle needs only to locate itself within the correct lane and keep the distance to the preceding vehicle. For this the camera is used to keep the vehicle within the driving lane and plan the vehicle motion in front of the vehicle. Radar and camera are used to avoid collisions with other vehicles. The AD vehicle is not able to operate if lane markings are missing; for this reason, the highway pilot function is typically constrained to highway roads. In order to enhance the accuracy when detecting the lane and plan the motion the module could also make use of cartography information to extract the geometry of the lanes ahead. The positioning is used to geofence the information from the cartography. For this purpose, the required absolute positioning accuracy is not high. Around ten meters absolute position is sufficient to fulfil the geo-fencing requirement.
 - Communication (V2X): external information is not used. In case of road anomalies, such as the presence of roadworks, the driver has to take the control of the vehicle and restart the AD system when the anomaly has passed.
 - Cybersecurity: the safety function relies on information coming from the in-vehicle sensors. No additional parameters should be taken into account rather than the traditional sensor monitoring system.
- SAE Level 3 and beyond highway pilot functionality: the AD function performs both longitudinal and lateral motion control and the system should continue to operate until the driver performs the fallback, which might take some time if the driver is not supervising the system.
 - Positioning: in such conditions, the system cannot rely only on the camera information; lane markings could disappear due to adverse weather conditions or road maintenance and the system must be able to drive until the driver takes the control. GNSS positioning, together with HD maps, is a solution that enables the vehicle to follow the road geometry without the assistance of the camera. In such conditions sub-meter absolute positioning is required.
 - Communication (V2X): information coming from the other vehicles and the infrastructure can be used to include into the data-fusion algorithm the presence of road anomalies (such as closed driving lanes or obstructed lanes) and to update the maps with dynamic change of road layout.
 - Cybersecurity: both GNSS and V2X signals are outside the vehicle domain control; data-trust is crucial to enable the vehicle to keep the information into account to develop safety application or a preventive autonomous driving disengagement.

2. Scenario parameter selection

In the following table the reasons are explained that should be taken into account to select the KET parameter. It is not a complete analysis but the principle that should be adopted to identify relevant parameters. Parameter definition is provided accordingly to HEADSTART deliverable D2.2 [3].

TABLE 1 EXAMPLE OF PARAMETERS IN THE DEFINITION OF THE “SHARED DIGITAL INFORMATION” OF SCENARIOS

KET domain	Parameter	Selection criteria
Positioning	Time To First Fix	Time To First Fix is not relevant for highway scenarios. The vehicle is typically active from several minutes before entering the motorway.
Positioning	Reacquisition Time (lack of GNSS fix)	Bridges, tunnels and other obstacles might be responsible for the lack of GNSS fix. Understanding the impact on the positioning module and the time necessary to recover the optimal performances are important.
Positioning	Position offset	The objective of this parameter changes based on the implemented AD functions: for SAE Level 2 highway pilot functionality it is important to analyse the system reaction if the vehicle, for whatever reason, is placed in a situation, where highway pilot functionality is not allowed. For SAE > Level 3 it should be validated what happens to the system when the GNSS signal drifts outside the real driving lane. The availability of clearly visible lane marking will also affect the AD vehicle function.
Communication (V2X)	Interoperability	Verify if the vehicle is able to decode messages following the specifications of the expected standard for the regions where the vehicle is supposed to drive.
Communication (V2X) /Cybersecurity	No usable V2X messages	Verify what happens when messages are generated with untrusted, outdated or corrupted payload. Note that the information could be simply dropped without activating any tell-tale lamp.
V2x/Cybersecurity	No usable V2X messages (V2X message not trustworthy)	Analyse system reaction to messages not trustworthy

2.3 Testing of scenarios

The scenario-based HEADSTART safety assessment methodology contains 4 different types of test methods, which will be described briefly in the sections below.

2.3.1 Field testing

Field testing, also referred to as open road testing, needs to be part of a coherent strategy that needs to be executed under a framework which maintains traceability of results between Field, Proving ground and Virtual testing.

The following figure shows the functional overview of the general methodology for CAD testing on public roads.

FIGURE 7 FIELD TESTING ON OPEN ROADS WITHIN THE HEADSTART METHODOLOGY

Field testing is integrated within the general framework, with its own particularities with respect to the other forms of testing: Virtual, XiL-based and Proving ground testing.

Field testing aims to test the “Driving Function”, under the requirements defined to specify the scenarios with special attention to the appropriate inclusion of Key Enabling Technologies concepts to the scene description. The evaluation is guided by the defined ODD, Minimum Risk Manoeuvres, Behaviour and any other specification to be validated. Field testing also imposes several additional considerations and constraints, as defined in section 4.1. Most importantly, Field testing is defined based on the following topics:

- Route selection: as discussed in next sub-section, this part includes the identification of suitable routes specific to test the target driving function, via the definition and description of criteria such as the presence or density of elements (perception blockers, VRUs density, etc.).
- Infrastructure requirements: provided the goal to run specific driving functions, technical requirements need to be in place. Particularly relevant are those requirements related to road infrastructure equipment or characteristics (e.g. availability of communication base stations, Differential-GPS services, etc.). Route-specific equipment or configurations might as well be needed at the instrumented vehicle, such as signal receivers, or V2I credentials.
- Driving function dependencies (other actives): in general, the driving function under test may need external actives to be present and considered, including other test/lead vehicles, existence of HD maps services for accurate localization functions, and/or updated standard definition maps for navigation.
- Regulation and exemptions: finally, Field testing utterly needs to be defined in the context of the regulatory, insurance and road-operation bodies that facilitate the testing activities under the mandated principles and regulations. In general, instrumented vehicles or functions under test need to acquire the necessary exemptions to be used in open roads.

Attending to the different testing methods (Virtual, Proving ground and XiL-based testing), Field testing needs to be defined to produce results which are evaluable with the same criteria, format and target. The goal is to guarantee that an effective test case coverage strategy can be executed spanning all forms of testing approaches, to monitor the extent and fulfilment of the test task itself. As a consequence, such coverage analysis can provide feedback on how many tests are still required, and in which form, defining the required resources (either computational, related to infrastructure, etc.).

A derived consequence of such harmonized methodology is the gained traceability across the different stages of the testing approach. When appropriate data and metadata repositories are created, test description and results can be queried, to enable identifying gaps, evaluate additional required efforts, or produce richer test results comparisons.

A detailed methodology for selecting the best route for Field testing is detailed in the deliverable D2.1 [1] of the HEADSTART project.

2.3.2 Virtual testing

In order to test scenarios virtually, a respective framework which enables the execution of appropriate scenario descriptions is necessary. A top-level overview of the general structure used for simulations of CAD systems are reflected in Figure 8. This approach can be seen as an appropriate modification of the classic *Sense-Plan-Act* – structure for model-based testing purposes, as the *Sense-Plan-Act* – structure is based on the *Driving Function*, adding the necessary blocks (*Sensors* and *Vehicle Dynamics*) for interaction with the environment. Every logical block can be either virtual or real, making this approach applicable for different test platforms and strategies.

The blocks have the following meaning:

- *Driving Function:*
It is the main part of this top-level approach framework. Implemented in an autonomous vehicle it is acting as the decision-maker of the whole system based on sensor input. The input from the *Sensors* block includes every sensor available to the system (e.g. LiDAR, Camera, GPS, IMU, ...). In which format the input is delivered highly depends on the sensor type and driving function. This can range from raw data to processed object-level data. If the driving function has decided on certain actions, based on the sensor input, the appropriate actions are transferred to the *Vehicle Dynamics* block.
- *Vehicle Dynamics:*
This block contains either the physical or virtual representation of the vehicle under test (VUT), equipped with the driving function. It takes the input from the driving function (driving commands) and acts accordingly. In case of a virtual model it is part of the virtual environment and underlies the respective physics engine and vehicle manoeuvres.
- *Sensors:*
This block gets all its input from the respective virtual environment. The model accuracy highly depends on the needed quality of sensor data, which then also reflects on the modelling approach for the virtual environment. In general, for the typical sensor used in autonomous systems, there are three types of modelling techniques, distinguished by abstraction level:
 - Ideal sensor models:
 - These models are generating object lists, which are based on perfect data from the virtual environment regarding objects like cars and vulnerable road users (VRU) in the sensors field of view. The models are simple enough to be easily used in real-time simulation environments and can be also used as simulation ground-truth data.
 - Probabilistic sensor models:
 - Based on ideal models and in order to cover aspects such as influence of weather conditions these types of models are adding statistical failure rates. Object list entries can be modified, or a certain level of noise can be added (depending on the kind of data).
 - Physical sensor models:
 - These kinds of models are based on the actual physical principles of the respective sensor type, hence the name. Thus, every type of sensor needs a different physical sensor model. Due to the complexity of these models, they require longer computation times which makes it more demanding and difficult to use for real-time simulations.

- Virtual Environment (including Scenario Modelling):
The virtual environment is where everything comes together and is represented in order to simulate the real world. Basically, it can be split in two different categories:
 - Static Environment:
 - In this category falls everything which does not change its location during scenario simulation. This includes surrounding objects like buildings and of course the whole road network, which is defined with the official standard OpenDRIVE [11].
 - Dynamic Environment:
 - Contrary to the static environment, the dynamic environment contains elements which could change its location during the scenario simulation (it could also include a parking vehicle). This includes mostly traffic objects like cars and VRUs.

In this block also the scenario modelling (applicable for scenario-based testing) can be placed in, as it defines how certain actors in the virtual environment move and/or react, as well as the road network on which the scenario is based upon in the OpenDRIVE standard. The scenario can be described with the official standard OpenSCENARIO, which is able to describe the actions of all actors in the virtual environment, which are participants of the scenario.

FIGURE 8 FRAMEWORK FOR VIRTUAL TESTING

A concrete application of the proposed framework for Virtual testing can be seen in Figure 9. In this implementation the functions (including driving function and sensor models) are connected to the rest of the framework with the Open Simulation Interface (OSI) [12] and/or the Functional Mock-up Interface [13]. These interfaces provide a standardized way to transfer relevant data. The defined functions are then integrated into the respective vehicle model, which acts then in the simulation, where the environment is defined with the means of OpenDRIVE and OpenSCENARIO.

FIGURE 9 VIRTUAL TESTING SCHEME: INTERFACING WITH HETEROGENEOUS COMPONENTS

In order to make virtual testing a reliable asset for validation strategies of CAD systems, the interfaces of the respective simulation framework need to make excessive use of existing or emerging standards. Such an approach guarantees that components from different sources (open source, vendor-specific, OEMs) can be used coherently within the same framework.

2.3.3 XiL-based testing

X-in-the-Loop (XiL) based testing is a type of testing offering a combination of real and virtual elements. The amount of virtual and real elements to the test can vary from having just a real driving function in a Hardware-in-the-Loop (HiL) lab to having several real participants on proving grounds and simulating just minor elements. Overall, XiL-based testing is a good compromise between Proving ground testing that is very realistic and Virtual testing that allows to test a higher number of scenarios.

In HEADSTART, special attention is paid to the Vehicle-in-the-Loop approach. Vehicle-in-the-Loop is the utilization of a real-world vehicle which is under test. With the vehicle under test being a real-world component, proving ground and other components can be real, too. However, at least some participants are simulated. This is done by giving virtual components to the driving function of the vehicle under test. Therefore, sensor simulations are necessary to be implemented and thus there has to be access to the internal systems of the driving function. Moreover, other combinations like HiL-tests are important to be mentioned.

In order to allow simulated participants to be part of a test case, these participants must be made available for the driving function under test. This is usually done by sensor simulations. A sensor simulation can range from physical models to phenomenological models. Physical models are not always necessary, especially if the perception and fusion are not under test. Statistical or phenomenological models are sufficient in these cases. Figure 10 shows an overview of HEADSTART's XiL-based testing approach.

FIGURE 10 XIL-BASED TESTING IN HEADSTART

The main idea of the XIL-based testing is to distribute the test on several tools depending on the degree of realism which is necessary for the specific component. The main input to the test is coming from OpenSCENARIO and OpenDRIVE, that are used for the description of a concrete scenario. The next step is to dynamically allocate the components of the scenario to the most suitable degree of realism. Components can be traffic participants, but also static environments, driver behaviour, specific sensors, HMI concepts, VRUs or others. To test such combination of arbitrary components in different tools and platforms a common framework is necessary. It turned out that the Open Simulation Interface (OSI) is a suitable candidate for most tasks. On top of that an underlying framework needs to provide synchronized and asynchronous message exchanges. Finally, a scenario control is necessary, which controls the execution of the test. This is needed due to the fact that all tools and components need to interpret and execute the test in the same way.

After test execution, not only the evaluation of the test results is an outcome, but there needs to be an analysis of the results to possibly reallocate the degrees of realism for the components. Especially, when a scenario is physically challenging for the driving function, which is not known before test execution, a reallocation of the ego vehicle to a real testing vehicle might be considered.

To include the HEADSTART KETs in the methodology of XIL-based testing, it is necessary to expand the approach. Since XIL-based testing is a combination of virtual elements and proving ground or Hardware-in-the-Loop tests, the simulation of KETs becomes a key element. The definitions used for the description of KETs can be reused for any type of testing. Positioning is either based on communication or is based on other layers and therefore implicitly included in the scenario. On top of that, cyberattacks are usually based on communication channels. Thus, the execution of tests on communication level is crucial for the testing of KETs. It can be challenging to test communication effects on the proving ground with real components, since the effects are very diverse. There is multi-path-propagation, shielding, reflection just to name a few when it comes to V2X communication. The effects are even more diverse; thus, a complete testing is challenging. However, within the simulation it is easier to simulate the effects of the named problems. It is not feasible to place a full city of buildings on proving grounds, but easy to implement in simulations. Thus, either the final effect like jitter, delay or replay can be tested with real components, but for a more detailed testing, scenarios need to be simulated when it comes to V2X communication.

2.3.4 Proving ground testing

Proving ground testing is a key part of the HEADSTART methodology for assessing the performance of the automated driving systems. Full system performance can be evaluated in these real-world environments while this is not feasible in Virtual testing or XiL-based testing because of their limitations. Physical testing presents real objects which are controlled with electronics platforms and allow to represent and test complex scenarios. This part of the overall methodology is the one with more fidelity to the real-world situations which are found on the roads during driving conditions, but the most expensive and complex to setup, execute and evaluate. They also are the ones with a higher risk for the human involved as well as for the vehicles under test and thus safety of the testing must be also considered.

The number of scenarios to be executed in test tracks will be determined by the limitation of the simulation environments and the complexity of the automated driving use cases. This means that very complex driving events should be reproduced in test tracks and this increases the complexity of the proving grounds preparation for this purpose, the necessary equipment and available physical (e.g. test tracks design, vertical and horizontal signage) and digital infrastructure (e.g. digital maps, communications infrastructure, GNSS augmentation information).

These new complex testing requirements for the proving grounds need to be managed in a very strategic manner in order to optimize the way the allocated tests are executed in the best cost and time effective manner.

Figure 11 shows an overview of the Proving ground testing methodology:

FIGURE 11 PROVING GROUND TESTING METHODOLOGY DIAGRAM

The methodology is divided in two main blocks:

1. Block 1: Generation of information / capabilities for “Allocation of Scenarios” subtask.
2. Block 2: Execution of concrete scenarios and test data generation in proving grounds.

Block 1

The main purpose of the first block is to generate information during the “Allocation of scenarios” subtask and this information will be used for defining which concrete scenarios will be allocated in proving grounds.

There are three main activities to be done during this block:

- Scenarios feasibility for Proving ground testing
- Vehicle dynamics models validation
- Sensors models validation

Block 2

Once the block 1 has been finished, the information about capabilities and fidelity of the sensor and dynamic models are provided to the “Allocation of scenarios” subtask and this will generate a batch of concrete scenarios according to the criteria defined in such subtask. These concrete scenarios will be the input to start the block 2 of the Proving ground testing methodology.

The main purpose of this block will be to define a strategy for the execution of the concrete scenarios in the best cost and time effective way.

There are two main activities during this block:

- Test strategy
- Test setup and execution

Once those two activities are finished, the test data is generated to be evaluated in the following step of the HEADSTART methodology “Evaluation of test results”.

2.4 Evaluation of test results

The evaluation step collects the output from all performed tests, compiles the results and evaluates the result versus pass/fail criteria’s and human capabilities as shown in Figure 2. Input to the pass/fail criteria come from the step before defining the test scenarios when use cases were decided based on Functional requirements, Abstract scenario descriptions and Requirements for KETs, and the driving function that is based on the ODD, the involved KETs, Minimum risk manoeuvre and Tactical manoeuvre behaviour. Information about chosen scenarios and type of tests performed (Virtual, XiL-based, Proving ground and Field testing) is expected to affect the evaluation. A view with evaluation focus is shown in Figure 12.

The evaluation is expected to be performed in a multi-step approach:

1. The results from each of the Field testing, Virtual testing, XiL-based testing and Proving ground testing are evaluated using KPIs (Key Performance Indicators) that are defined based on input requirements.
2. After evaluating versus KPIs the test results are compiled.
3. The compiled results are evaluated based on pass/fail criteria and human capabilities (Inclusion of human capabilities into the methodology is out of the scope of the HEADSTART project).

Pass/fail criteria

Pass/fail criteria for evaluating the result of the test may be of several kinds:

- **Threshold** criteria will be the most straight-forward approach if there is a clear limit for what must be achieved; e.g. the response time must not be longer than 500 ms for the test to be assessed as “Pass”.
- **Rating** criteria in steps may be used to summarize a complex test result. There must be a description of what is required at every step of the rating; e.g. a ‘star rating’ where the assessment is given in five steps with maximum five stars.

- **Measured values** may be used to describe a test result; e.g. the maximum speed for which the vehicle performance is kept is recorded as 65 km/h.
- **Reaction** of the vehicle must be described for some tests, often in combination with a measure to describe how well the vehicle under test has passed the test; e.g. “Pass”, since the vehicle reacts to the loss of performance by reducing the maximum speed to 30 km/h as minimum risk manoeuvre.

Requirements for the three HEADSTART KETs have been compiled in deliverable D1.3 [14] with functional requirements described at vehicle level. Technical constraints were described at vehicle component level. Safety requirements for road-users were described. Requirements not related to safety, such as requirements for comfort and efficiency, are excluded from the tests. The methodology for the evaluation of test results has been described in deliverable D2.1 [1]. Tests must be assessed with metrics regardless of the assessment methodology and the purpose. Examples of such metrics are time to collision and ego vehicle position. Sixteen new parameters have been identified and are further described by HEADSTART requirements (D2.2 [3]); divided into Positioning, Communication (V2X) and Cybersecurity. The three KETs are then addressed for Proving ground testing, Virtual testing, XiL-based testing and Field testing, starting from the user-needs identified in D1.3 (chapter 3.1) [14]. Testing requirements are given for Proving ground testing, Virtual testing, XiL-based testing and Field testing on open roads.

The requirements also must be applied differently for different scenarios, and the most appropriate scenarios have to be selected depending on the purpose of the test. The in-depth application to use cases and scenarios is not in the scope of this chapter. The requirements may be applied differently in the different use cases since the hazards will be different. Requirements may be applicable for all use cases, but the criteria for a successful test result may differ. In some cases, a straightforward pass/fail criterion will be enough. In other cases, the result may best be expressed in a scale. The purpose of the test will also affect the test plan; development testing, consumer testing or homologation testing will affect both the number of requirements, the test methods, the extension of the test and the evaluation criteria.

FIGURE 12 ALTERNATIVE VIEW OF TEST RESULT EVALUATION

2.5 Cybersecurity

The HEADSTART project considers Cybersecurity as a KET together with Positioning and Communication (V2X). The reasoning for treating Cybersecurity as a KET is that all three are technologies with the equal degree of importance where HEADSTART intends to propose a harmonized validation method. Therefore, HEADSTART integrates KETs, especially Cybersecurity, into the safety validation methodology.

Such achievement was presented in HEADSTART deliverable “D2.2. Extension of the Common Methodology for the HEADSTART Key Enabling Technologies” [3] by identifying parameters and testing requirements for KETs. At that moment, the project was handling an intention to harmonize KETs with an integrated KET enrichment activity. In such activity, KETs could introduce new parameters to enhance specific scenarios. The extension of these scenario parameters provided a better understanding of the future possible testing scenarios and introduced KETs in the scenarios as a relevant technology to improve the comprehension of the environment. However, finding parameters for cybersecurity was an almost impossible challenge that forced us to redefine the framework of parameters definition. In the end, the selected parameters were designed to generate a bridge between the list of threats and the test cases. A methodology is needed for testing requirements using a preselected list of parameters and thus generate test cases to introduce cybersecurity tests in the different testing methods (e.g. penetration test, functional and interface test, fuzzy test, vulnerability scanning, etc...). The inclusion of such parameters turned the initial scenario to a concrete KET enhanced scenario ready for testing, ultimately leading to the evaluation part of the methodology.

The enrichment of the common HEADSTART methodology by the KETs provides an integrated and unified solution for the methodology. However, cybersecurity coverage for safety validation of CAD vehicles is not complete. In contrast to the other two KETs, which in general are considered tangible and easier to measure/test, it is difficult to measure and apply any type of performance indicators. Positioning and Communication (V2X) are KETs that refer to specific functionalities, and such functionalities can be added to test in the KETs extension activity. However, cybersecurity does not have specific functionality, it is a state of the system, in this case, the state of the CAD vehicle and its systems, where the system is protected against criminal or unauthorized attacks, providing measures to achieve this.

Therefore, cybersecurity needs a special treatment to be integrated into the safety assessment in HEADSTART methodology. To cover this specific KET, it is necessary to introduce into the methodology a specific cybersecurity activity. Such activity should cover:

- Product development, requirements, and architectural design.
- Guidance of documents for preparation and operation of the cybersecurity systems (target of evaluation)
- Cybersecurity throughout the lifecycle of the systems (development and maintenance).
- Tests for developing testing (coverage and depth), functional testing and independent testing.
- Vulnerability analysis.
- Cybersecurity as measurable and composable context.

FIGURE 13 CYBERSECURITY ASSESSMENT IN HEADSTART

Cybersecurity assessment in the methodology provides a special activity to carry out all the tasks required for the complete cybersecurity evaluation (see Figure 13). Cybersecurity assessment activities are based on the Common Criteria (CC) international standard [15] for evaluating the security properties of IT products. The CC defines a framework for evaluation oversight, the structure for specifying security requirements and a methodology for evaluating those requirements. Furthermore, target groups can implement and request security attributes of their systems, e.g. into vehicle-specific cybersecurity assets, and hire testing laboratories to evaluate their products and determine if they meet these requests. The CC ensures that the process of specification, implementation and evaluation of a computer security product has been carried out in a rigorous, standard and repeatable manner at a level consistent with the security assurance level defined for the target groups within the defined environment for use.

The philosophy of the cybersecurity assessment is providing assurance levels through different evaluation activities and techniques. Such activities and techniques are mainly analysis of processes and procedures and checks that they are being applied, analysis of the correspondence between representations of the system design and analysis of such design against the requirements, verification of proofs, analysis of guidance documents, analysis of functional test and its results, independent functional testing, analysis of vulnerabilities and penetration testing. Such techniques will depend on the security assurance level defined by the target group before starting the cybersecurity assessment and it will depend on the scope (the item definition under evaluation), the depth (the level of fineness of design and implementation detail) and the rigour (the higher degree of structured and formal manner).

The activities needed to complete the cybersecurity assessment are based on the CC approach and are tailored to the purpose of HEADSTART. There are three main activities that correlate with the target group.

The first activity carries out the generation of specific security needs for the target of evaluation and represents the tasks that the developer (OEMs, Tiers-n and carmakers) must perform during the development of the system (called in CC, target of evaluation) and its application in the vehicle. It is an implementation-dependent statement of security needs and defines the information assurance security and the functional requirements for a specific identified target of evaluation. This step provides a complete and rigorous description of a security problem in terms of target of evaluation description, threats, assumptions, security objectives, secure functional

requirements, security assurance requirements, and rationales. Furthermore, it contains information that demonstrates how the product addresses the security requirements based on the generic security requirements selected for each system.

The second activity introduces the role of independent laboratories to provide independent evidence of the cybersecurity activities of the evaluated system. A CC testing laboratory is a third-party commercial security testing facility that is accredited to conduct security evaluations for conformance to the CC international standard. Such facility must be accredited according to ISO/IEC 17025 [16] with its national certification body and, furthermore, comply with the specific requirements enforced by each country.

Finally, the last activity is the certification of the target of evaluation and its specific security needs. The results of the independent testing laboratories together with the specific security need are certified by the cybersecurity authority of each country and represented by the type approval target group of HEADSTART.

The details of the activities are explained in the cybersecurity representation of the process, in the next WP3, more specifically in the HEADSTART deliverable “D3.1. Guideline of a comprehensive validation and certification procedure to ensure safe CAD systems” [17].

Use cases and cybersecurity

The introduction of the cybersecurity assessment in the methodology allows the project to connect cybersecurity with the different selected HEADSTART use cases. Most of the activities that cybersecurity assessment needs to perform must be performed independently to the use cases. However, the scenarios are slightly different between each use cases and that could affect to the vulnerabilities of the system and its test cases generation.

There are three use cases selected in HEADSTART: Truck platooning, Highway pilot and Traffic jam chauffeur. Such different use cases are covered by the cybersecurity assessment and as mentioned above, do not affect cybersecurity assessment activities. However, there is a group of assets that could be affected, and especially, there is one that has important relevance in our project, the Communication (V2X) KET. Communication (V2X) has different purposes and functionalities in each use case, and this indirectly affects the generation of the test cases.

The Communication (V2X) has common functionalities for each use case, nevertheless, there are special functionalities that must be mentioned for each one of them. For example, for the Truck platooning use case, the most important functionality is communication between trucks. Since the trucks follow each other, it is required to provide specific requirements to achieve a certain communication performance. It is slightly different from the Traffic jam chauffeur use case, where communication is not just established between cars, but it can have an important role for the user equipment (i.e. mobile phone) since it can introduce other services like management of the traffic flow or routing. The role of the user equipment is also important for the Highway pilot use case because it can have the same functionalities as the Traffic jam chauffeur use case. However, in this case, communication has a strong focus on providing information services like emergency situations or temporal changes on the road. In the end, all three use cases can have their own functionalities and impact on the cybersecurity test cases but at the same time, its rather impossible to provide a clear separation between them. Therefore, HEADSTART gives to the user the freedom to generate their own test cases and does not introduce a specific task to the selected use cases. This will be further elaborated in WP3 and WP4 of the HEADSTART project.

2.6 Methodology implications related to type approval and national legislation

Current admittance regulations take into account a system that performs automated driving tasks within humans dominated traffic, currently only in one specific use case: An Automated Lane Keeping System (ALKS) on a highway up to a maximum speed of 60 km/h. New elements as Human Factors (take over requests), automated dynamic driving tasks, Operational Domain are prescribed in a first UN Regulation [18]. The check of the system performance within the type approval procedure is based on Proving ground testing by the technical service and

by the evaluation of test results delivered by the manufacturer. Virtual testing additionally to the Proving ground tests may be applied as well. However, Field tests have been recently included in its latest draft (see Section 3.3.2 for more information).

It is important to state that for a vehicle authority allowing open road trials (Field testing) would serve multiple purposes. Primarily it is intended to gain knowledge and ensure appropriate new regulation. Secondly, it is to check whether the technology is indeed capable of safely taking over human driving tasks. Thirdly, it aims to improve the admission process leading to new legislation. And finally, it is intended to allow new methods and techniques for validation (for example the increasing role of Virtual testing or testing by driving in real traffic (Field testing)).

National Admittance Procedure (NAP)

The National Admittance Procedure for Experimental Automated Vehicles (NAP) is an integrated approach by authorities in the Netherlands, that includes building blocks needed for the safe temporary use of experimental automated vehicles on national open roads, pending formal European legislation. Building blocks are usable elements from European Type Approval, national legislation, national schemes for Field testing on open roads and insights from authorities dealing with traffic safety. The NAP can function as an umbrella, where countries can add or remove building blocks to suit local requirements. The NAP described in this chapter is not part of HEADSTART's basic methodology. However, due to its relevance in the Dutch homologation process it is presented in the following.

High over, the NAP takes the following principles into consideration:

- A vehicle consists of mechanics and IT.
- Driving tasks can be performed by human and system.
- Humans will be on the road for the coming decades.
- The traffic system is the starting point, not the vehicle (behaviour, vehicle, infrastructure (OD)).
- It's about showing safe and predictable automated driving behaviour related to human performance, in open traffic.
- The vehicle has to anticipate to certain (scenarios) and uncertain / unforeseen (skills) circumstances.
- The human driver/operator is always in a position to prevent or correct misjudgements or misperception resulting in harmful events. (Safe Transition of Control. Considering other road users.)
- Performance based requirements / standards (where possible no technical solutions prescribed).
- It is not about passing or failing, but about estimating the maturity of the system. More or less restrictions are imposed depending on the maturity. It is a stepped approach, a growing path.
- The applicant is accountable / liable / moral responsible.

The NAP is an integrated procedure for the safe temporary admittance of experimental automated vehicles on national open roads, that has an iterative / adaptive / evaluative character (learning circles), where requirements are aligned with the complexity of the in-vehicle IT systems (dedicated software, hardware and sensors) and the automated driving tasks within an Operational Domain (OD), and where the customer / applicant understands that for the coming time admittance rules can change due to the learning cycles.

The admittance process can be seen as a learning cycle, as shown in Figure 14.

FIGURE 14 NAP AS A LEARNING CYCLE

Below a number of process steps are briefly explained. The building blocks will be explained more extensive.

Process steps:

1. Checklist for applicants: experience has shown that a checklist is necessary because of the complexity of the process. It is also a check to see if the application is serious. In depth questions about the vehicle, the needed Operational Domain and automated driving tasks to be trailed on open roads are asked.
2. Application: the formal application. This includes an initial hazard analysis and risk assessment (HARA) from the applicant.
3. Pre-risk assessment: the vehicle authority assesses the application and makes a first assumption on risk classification, needed to estimate the severity of the admittance procedure later on.
4. Intake: the pre-risk assessment is shared with the applicant.
5. Start meeting: in this meeting all information is shared with all stakeholders involved. E.g. applicant, vehicle authority, road authority, law enforcement, research institutes on road safety, etc are present at the meeting.

Outcome is a shared understanding of the trail itself, the risks involved and the knowledge questions that can be answered by conducting the trials on open roads.

6. After the start meeting the risk classification is finalized. The classification depends, among others, on the maturity of the vehicle (type approved parts), the complexity of the operational domain, the complexity and maturity of the driving tasks, the capacity of the human driver to safely take over when needed, and results of earlier trials.
7. Testing / Admittance: starting from the risk classification the building blocks are used to test the vehicle. See for more details below.
8. Exemption / License: when the vehicle passes all tests, a national exemption or license is issued. With this document, which is time and place restricted, the applicant can begin the trials on open roads.
9. Reporting: the applicant shares relevant information of the trail.
10. Evaluating: the trail is evaluated, including the risk assessment, the knowledge questions about the trail itself, but also learning points for the admittance procedure.
11. Learning points: important learning points are used to improve the admittance procedure. Main reason is to continuously reduce risk. This may mean that previous successful applications will not get an exemption the next time.

Building blocks

Building blocks are usable elements from European Type Approval, national legislation, national schemes for Field testing on open roads and insights from authorities dealing with traffic safety. In this deliverable the Dutch approach is explained as an example. Other countries can add or remove building blocks to suit local requirements.

1. European Type Approval

Europe has an EU type approval system. It provides EU countries with a common set of rules for the approval of motor vehicles and their trailers and of systems, components and separate technical units intended for these vehicles. It makes type approval compulsory for all categories of whole vehicles, including those built in several stages. It lays down:

- a harmonized framework with general technical requirements for the type approval of new vehicles and of systems, components and technical units designed for such vehicles, so as to facilitate their registration, sale and entry into service in the EU;
- rules regarding the sale and entry into service of vehicle parts and equipment.

The directive mainly covers the administrative procedure to be followed for the approval of vehicles. The actual technical requirements against which vehicles have to be tested are covered in other EU texts which are listed in Annex IV to the directive. The directive (“2018/858 /EC — approval of motor vehicles and their trailers, and of systems, components and separate technical units intended for such vehicles”) can be found on the EUR-Lex website [19].

Important for field trials:

- Current possibilities for partial automated driving (SAE Level 2) are only driver assist systems (e.g. park assist, continuous lane keeping, adaptive cruise control).
- End of June 2020 it was adopted that Automated Lane Keeping Systems (ALKS) are within the Type Approval from the year 2021 onwards. ALKS is an automated driving system (SAE Level 3) which is activated by the driver and which keeps the vehicle within its lane for travelling speed of 60 km/h or less by controlling the lateral and longitudinal movements of the vehicle for extended periods without the need for further driver input or permanent surveillance by the driver [18].
- A vehicle authority can, for automated driving, determine nationally which part of the directive should be obliged and which can be skipped, depending on the requested trail. For example, in the Netherlands

electromagnetic compatibility (EMC) is always mandatory. The part directive R79 about steering could be partially skipped for shuttles as they have no steering column.

- Regulation is compliance based. It is improved by learning from accidents in the past. Although easy to enforce and predictable, it prescribes the technical requirements, and was not applicable to unforeseen situations in the past. This is changing now with the Regulation for ALKS and partly with the latest amendments to some other Regulations. With ALKS being the first Level 3 automated driving system, which is allowed to fulfil a complete and defined driving task for a certain period of time and releases the driver from its obligations for this driving task, the requirements laid down in the Regulation also include behaviour rules of traffic laws for driving. Therefore, also the technical requirements are described in a more generally applicable way and not only for special situations, in order to cover almost all common driving situations and in principal to require from the system to master all situations during its driving period.

2. Article 20

The EU has an exemption procedure (Article 20). New technologies for which no rules yet exist or that do not fit into the existing regulations can still be admitted to the EU market through an exception procedure, often in anticipation of amendments to the legislation and regulations that are already in the making, when a request is made by a member state, it is adopted by the other member states, under the direction of the EU Commission. This requires a quantitative and qualitative foundation that shows that safety and environmental performance remain at least the same.

The final regulations that such innovations must comply with may deviate from what was previously permitted via this exception procedure, while in that case production must be adjusted. Normally, the effective dates of new and adapted legislative steps are known in advance enough to allow manufacturers to get production in order.

For more information on article 20, visit the EUR-Lex website [20]. From September 2020, article 20 will be replaced by article 39 [21].

Important for field trials:

- Article 20 is only applicable for OEMs, and for technologies or concepts which are incompatible with one or more regulatory acts. It replaces a system, component or technical unit that is already been described in the regulations. E.g. article 20 was used for testing cameras instead of mirrors, which is now in regulation.
- Regulation is compliance based.

3. National regulations

The tasks, responsibilities and competences of a vehicle authority is stated in national law. For the Netherlands this is:

- The road traffic act ('wegenverkeerswet') [22]. Describes the tasks, responsibilities and authorizations of the authorities dealing with road safety.
- Regulation on traffic signs and traffic rules ('reglement verkeerstekens en verkeersregels') [23]. Describes the rules and desired behaviour for traffic participants.
- Vehicle regulation ('regeling voertuigen') [24]. Describes the translation from European Type Approval to national regulations regarding vehicles.

Important for field trials:

- National regulations are almost always a direct translation of the European type approval.
- A vehicle authority can, for automated driving, determine nationally which law should be obliged and which can be skipped, depending on the requested trail.
- A vehicle authority can restrict the admission in time and place for safety reasons.

- Regulation is compliance based.

4. Dutch: Vehicle Safety & Security Framework (VSSF)

The Vehicle Safety and Security Framework (VSSF) is RDW's initial step towards standardizing the process of approving in-vehicle hard- and software. The Vehicle Safety and Security Framework constitutes a methodology for handling aspects like cybersecurity, functional safety, software development, software updates among others that are vital for development of Connected and Automated Vehicles (CAVs). The framework consists of best practices from relevant domains. The Framework is built around Process Assessment, Product validation, Post approval and Advanced developments:

FIGURE 15 VSSF

Every item has questions for a manufacturer to answer. Based on the answers, the maturity of the IT system can be estimated. At this point, it is a self-assessment tool. In total there are more than 300 questions. Below is an example for the item Functional Safety:

Maturity & Compliancy Check questions // Functional Safety

#	Compliance check - please indicate if you have policies or documentation for the following elements	We have policies or documentation
FS1	Competence management/ Resource management/Roles and Responsibilities	No
1	How would you describe the overall safety process and assignment of responsibilities during the occurrence of anomalies? A) We do not have a clear process or approach in place B) There is clear process in place but it is unclear who is responsible and accountable within the organisation C) There is a clear process in place and there is appropriate accountability throughout the organisation	Please indicate with X (only one selection possible)
2	How would you describe the competence management with regards to functional safety in your organisation? A) We have sufficient knowledge and expertise of vehicle, system or components with regards to functional safety B) The required information on functional safety is always available C) We use proven functional safety-related methods, tools and guidelines D) We have a training program specific to functional safety (including appropriate certifications) E) Organizational specific processes and policies with regards to functional safety	Please indicate with X (multiple selections possible)
3	Do you have an organisational process in place to assign the appropriate roles and responsibilities with respect to product development and post product development to ensure functional safety? A) Yes B) Partially C) No	Please indicate with X (only one selection possible)
FS2	Quality management system	No
4	Do you have quality management system in place (as per ISO/TS 16949, ISO 9001, or equivalent)? A) Yes B) No	Please indicate with X (only one selection possible)
FS3	Safety Plan, Culture and Coverage across Lifecycle	No
5	Which of the following statements are true with regards to the safety culture for your organisation? A) There is a proactive collaboration culture with regards to safety B) Senior management is accountable for and committed to decisions with regards to safety C) Safety has a high priority throughout the lifecycle of the vehicle or components D) We have continuous organisational learning with regards to safety through practices such as feedback systems, monitoring, and analysis E) The appropriate amount of resources are always dedicated to safety by (senior) management	Please indicate with X (multiple selections possible)

FIGURE 16 FUNCTIONAL SAFETY QUESTIONS (PART)

Important for field trials:

- In the Netherlands, elements from the VSSF can be applicable for field trials. Functional Safety and Cybersecurity are mandatory. Safety of the Intended Functionality (SOTIF [25]) is becoming mandatory.
- VSSF regulation is compliance based.

5. Dutch: Vehicle Driving License Framework (VDLF)

The Vehicle Driving License Framework (VDLF) is RDW's initial step towards standardizing the process of approving automated driving behaviour. As already mentioned in HEADSTART deliverable D2.1 "Common methodology for test, validation and certification" [1], for a vehicle authority the open roads are the end goal of automated driving. On open roads (i.e. Field testing), with real traffic and real road users a government can only admit vehicles that perform the driving task in a safe and predictable manner.

There are different possible ways to include real world driving for the approval of automated vehicles and the international discussion for a harmonised way is still ongoing. One possibility would be the Dutch proposal to include the real world driving into the national driving license framework of each Country to somehow get a digital driving licence for the automated vehicle. Another possibility would be to include the real world driving of the vehicles into the approval process with the applicable Regulations in addition to tests on proving grounds and Virtual testing.

Scenario based approach and skills

The VDLF incorporates the data-driven scenario-based approach for the validation and verification of automated driving functions. These scenarios are tested via Virtual, XiL-based, Proving ground and Field testing.

Although the advantage of scenarios is that the driving task can be described and programmed objectively, a disadvantage is that millions of scenarios have to be devised and are needed to drive an automated vehicle. An even greater disadvantage is that unexpected situations cannot be captured in scenarios. Scenarios are reactive. For many different situations the system needs skills to distract what the best thing is to do in a given situation at hand. Traffic is an open system that involves risks. People learn to anticipate unexpected circumstances and predict how the situation can develop. For example, if another road user makes a mistake, e.g. not giving priority. With Artificial Intelligence it seems possible to program this anticipatory behaviour. But AI for automated driving is still in an experimental phase, so results are yet to come.

Depending on the traffic situation, the software has to deduce what is 'best to do' at that time. These skills are proactive in relation to the learning of scenarios and are not tied to specific situations. Making qualitative requirements for safe and predictable traffic behaviour is the biggest challenge for vehicle authorities, being used to quantitative requirements as used in the current type approval. Learning from traffic exams for humans can be a way forward.

The Framework

Virtual testing, Proving ground testing and the driving exam respectively are a mean to a goal: safe admission of automated vehicles. The VDLF is one possibility of the building blocks towards an admittance procedure for automated driving:

FIGURE 17 VDLF

The framework consists of four steps:

1. Virtual testing:
 - A 'digital twin world' (OD) for a specific use case (e.g. highway pilot functionality).
 - With a broad set of traffic scenarios.
 - Simulation of the software driver interacting in these scenarios.
 - Outcome is related to the average human performance and risk profiles within the tested operational domain (OD).
 - For understanding the automated traffic behaviour.
 - Virtual test tools should be open and available together with the virtual vehicle and driver model for all contracting parties.
2. Proving ground testing:
 - To make sure the software and hardware are integrated well by the manufacturer, a real-life test on a closed proving ground is performed for validation purposes.
 - Happy flow tests and stress tests.
 - Different scenarios than the virtual ones.
 - Test the same scenarios for validation purposes.
3. Driving exam:
 - an objective, reproducible driving test, within the prescribed OD, to guarantee the level playing field for manufacturers.
 - An exam on public roads.
 - In this exam traffic situations should be negotiated positively.
 - Validation of safe interaction in complex traffic situations (scenarios and skills) within the OD.
 - Task of an examiner/authority: determines whether the displayed behaviour deviates from what is expected. Depending on the nature and severity of the deviant behaviour and the number of times it occurs, the software driver is or is not fit to drive.
4. Monitoring (in use conformity):
 - Monitoring: e.g. abnormal behaviour (ignoring traffic rules or endangering other road users), unsafe software updates, hacking or malicious software.
 - Monitoring is used to determine whether the use on the public road remains within the boundaries of the risk analysis. By monitoring, the authorities can iteratively improve the admittance process.

Important for field trials:

- VDLF regulation is performance based. The system is seen as a black box, and only the desired outcome is prescribed. By being output driven, it allows for different solutions and means of compliance. Disadvantages are that it requires fundamental insight in the traffic system and is more difficult to set-up.

6. Dutch: exemptions and permits

The Testing / Admittance step in the NAP is where the actual admittance testing is taking place. Depending on the risk classification, an estimate is made which elements from the building blocks are going to be used. Not every trail has the same risk profile. This depends, among others, on the complexity of the operational domain and the complexity of the automated driving task.

Below is an example of use cases plotted in a matrix. The more complex the driving task, the more elements of the building blocks need to be used to guarantee the safe temporary use of experimental automated vehicles (the colours are an indication for when legislation is needed):

FIGURE 18 USE CASES IN A COMPLEXITY MATRIX

The admittance of an automated shuttle is used as an example to explain the choices being made. In this case, the shuttle uses a fixed route at low speed. Being on the open roads, it has to deal with other traffic (pedestrians and cyclists).

Type approval:

The first estimate is the percentage possibility of UNECE compliance specific for this trial. Being innovative vehicles, the estimation is an expert judgement and tailored to the specific trial. See a part of the outcome below as an example. Where compliance could not be met, a risk analysis based on ISO 26262 [8] or SOTIF [25] was required.

number	subject	regulation	number	percentage possibility of UN-ECE-compliance	reason percentage compl
				percentage	
1A	noise level	UN - ECE Regulation	51	90	no accelerator pedal pres
3B	rear under run device	UN - ECE Regulation	58	100	
4A	rear registration place space	EU - Regulation	1003-2010	100	
5A	steering equipment	UN - ECE Regulation	79	60	no fysical steeringwheel p
6A	vehicle acces and manoevrability	EU - Regulation	130-2012	100	
7A	audible warning horn	UN - ECE Regulation	28	100	
8A	devices for indirect vision	UN - ECE Regulation	46	0	vehicle no fixed Y point dr
9A	braking vehicles	UN - ECE Regulation	13	75	vehicle without abs and n
10A	electronic compatibility EMC	UN - ECE Regulation	10	100	

FIGURE 19 EXAMPLE: COMPLIANCE WITH TYPE APPROVAL

National regulations:

The operational domain was established in collaboration with the road authority. National regulation is used to restrict the admission in time and place. The shuttle in this example did not have windshield wipers so it was restricted from driving in the rain.

Within national regulation, a vehicle authority is allowed to conduct necessary test to make sure the vehicle is safe. In this case, the vehicle was tested based on the Hazard Analysis and Risk Assessment (HARA, ISO 26262, SOTIF). A verification test plan was made by RDW (happy flow testing, stress testing, penetration testing, behaviour testing, security), and physically conducted. This resulted in a test report.

The industry uses the following documents the most:

- UL4600 Standard for Safety for the Evaluation of Autonomous Products (2019) [26]
- NHTSA Functional Safety Assessment of an Automated Lane Centering System (2018) [27]
- Safety First for Automated Driving (SaFAD) white paper (2019) [28]

VSSF

For the shuttle, the questions for Functional Safety, SOTIF and Cybersecurity Engineering were asked. For trials Product Validation, Post Approval and Advanced Developments are out of scope.

VDLF

From the VDLF the Proving ground testing process step and the monitoring (in service conformity) was used. In this step, collaboration was sought with the Dutch bureau for driving exams, CBR. When looking at the traffic behaviour of the shuttle, the automated driver should perform as a human driver: drive at such speed that it is adapted to the other traffic and the total traffic- or road situation and that no danger or unnecessary hindrance for other road users arises or can arise.

Below are the most important items that were monitored during the trail:

		Essential:
Road worthiness	Self control (sensors / actuators / lightning / tire pressure / fuel or battery / surroundings) Preparation (route planning / traffic / special circumstances / weather conditions)	
Traffic participation	Anticipatory driving behavior (flow / awareness of mistakes from others) Obeying traffic laws Show desirable driving behavior (NL: article 5 WvW (Road traffic law)) (defensive and vigilant) Especially children, the elderly, the deaf, the blind, cyclists Traffic insight: Concrete traffic situations Situations that are going to develop Situations that can develop in a certain way	Interest of other road users / viewing behaviour / giving priority / place on road / distance / speed / reaction to lights and signs /

FIGURE 20 DRIVING TASK

Admittance

In the Netherlands, there are two possibilities to admit automated vehicles to open roads:

- Exemption: for trials with vehicles where the human driver/steward is in the vehicle.
- Permit: for trials with vehicles where the human driver/steward is outside the vehicle (e.g. in a control room).

A third possibility is being researched: a driving license for the vehicle, as described in above sections.

3 Specifying methodology for selected HEADSTART use cases

In the paragraphs below the HEADSTART safety assessment methodology described in chapter 2 will be applied to the HEADSTART use cases presented in paragraph 1.3; Highway pilot, Truck platooning and Traffic jam chauffeur. Each of the steps of the assessment will be discussed in more detail for that specific use case, where current limitations and/or gaps will be briefly described. Special attention will be paid to the three HEADSTART KETs; Communication (V2X), Positioning and Cybersecurity, as well as the different test methods; Virtual testing, XiL-based testing, Proving ground testing and Field testing.

3.1 Highway pilot

The Highway pilot use case can be defined as the Conditional (SAE Level 3) or Highly Automated Driving (SAE Level 4) in non-congested conditions, on highways and other structurally separated roads, with a speed range of 30 km/h to 130 km/h.

It allows the driver to turn attention away from the driving task for a longer period, since the driver is not responsible to monitor the environment. The vehicle handles all the driving-related tasks, e.g. changing lanes to overtake slower vehicles. Potentially, driving in tunnels or through toll gates could be excluded, depending on the exact system specification. In addition, the system initiates the process of returning responsibility back to the driver, if operating in SAE Level 3. In emergency situations the functions execute defined actions:

At SAE Level 3: In case of a takeover request to the driver from the system, the driver has enough time reserved to orientate themselves and take over the driving task. In case the driver does not take over, the system will go to a reduced risk condition, i.e. bring the vehicle to a safe stop. If possible, depending on the traffic situation and system capabilities, the reduced risk conditions will include the necessary lane changes to stop at the hard shoulder e.g. emergency lane or side of the road.

At SAE Level 4: There is no request from the system to the driver to take over when the system is in normal operation area (i.e. on the motorway). In case a situation occurs, where a human driver would try to end the journey or simply stop at the motorway (e.g. extreme weather) and the driver does not take over, the system has the capability to leave the motorway and park the vehicle safely [29].

The main benefits of this use case for the consumers are the added comfort while driving as well as the possibility to focus on something other than the driving task. For the OEMs, this use case is more straightforward to implement than other use cases (e.g. urban driving) because the scenarios encountered are more structured, even at high speed.

A crosscheck was made with HEADSTART deliverable D1.3 [14] and D1.4 [4] containing requirements on testability of the KETs. The Highway pilot use case is particularly useful for testing the KETs Positioning and Cybersecurity.

As a use case description usually encompasses many different reference implementations, also many different descriptions of the Operational Design Domain (ODD) belonging to a Highway pilot use case exist. The following table describes one possible specification for a Highway pilot use case:

TABLE 2 EXAMPLE SPECIFICATION FOR HIGHWAY PILOT USE CASE SCENARIO

Entry	Value
Area of operation	Open Roads, mixed traffic

Entry	Value
Road Type	Highway or other structurally separated roads Other characteristics: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • No traffic in the opposite direction on the road (structurally separated roads) • Limited access: motorized vehicles and trucks (but pedestrians or cyclists may occur) • With or without toll gate • No intersections and no traffic lights (except some tunnels or bridges) May be included for country-specific use cases (e.g. USA, Canada)
Admissible Road Infrastructure	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Roads, tunnels, vicinity of highway entry/exit, overpasses • No work zone
Dedicated infrastructure	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Clear lane markings (e.g. with reflective paint) and visible road signs are needed • No connectivity V2I needed but possible (e.g. toll gate or work zone warning) • HD map with regular updates (future development)
Traffic Density	Highway pilot functionality = Fluid traffic
Speed Range	From 30 km/h to 130 km/h
Environmental Conditions (This describes potential parameters whose values need to be extracted from the respective ODD.)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Min visibility of X → no fog, no snow (no use of fog lamp) • Min friction coefficient of X → no heavy rain and snow • The vehicle cannot drive under extreme weather condition (heavy rain, snow, fog ...) • The function can work both in day and night-time.
Vehicle Configuration (This includes potential vehicle configurations that could be equipped with a highway pilot function)	Passenger cars with a maximum gross vehicle mass up to 3500 kg Truck with a mass of 12 to 44 t.

Other representations of an ODD for a Highway pilot use case can be found in “A Framework for Automated Driving System Testable Cases and Scenarios” [30], both for SAE Level 3 Conditional Automated Highway Drive and SAE Level 4 Highly Automated Highway Drive.

Based on the defined ODD it is possible to identify important objects and events that automated driving systems could encounter within the ODD. This is commonly referred to as object and event detection and response (OEDR) and is part of the dynamic driving task, as defined in (SAE J3016 [10]). An example of such a mapping (specific event with respective response) for a conditional automated highway function can be seen in Table 3 and is adopted from “A Framework for Automated Driving System Testable Cases and Scenarios” [30].

TABLE 3 EVENT AND RESPONSE MAPPING FOR CONDITIONAL AUTOMATED HIGHWAY DRIVE FEATURE

Event	Response
Lead vehicle decelerating	Follow vehicle, decelerate, stop, change lane, pass
Lead vehicle stopped	Decelerate, stop, change lane, pass
Lead vehicle accelerating	Accelerate ¹ , follow vehicle
Ego vehicle cutting in	Yield, decelerate, stop, follow vehicle, change lane
Lead vehicle cutting out	Accelerate ¹ , decelerate, stop
Ego vehicle changing lanes	Yield, decelerate, accelerate ¹ , follow vehicle, change lane

The presented table is focused on events regarding roadway users (other traffic participants) but it can be extended (based on the description of the actual driving function and the respective ODD) to non-roadway users as well as traffic signs and signals (if applicable). Scenario selection and allocation

Various national databases exist which contain useful information regarding scenarios on the highway. The database StreetWise [31] from TNO can provide scenarios in the output formats OpenDRIVE and OpenSCENARIO and contains recorded data for more than 1000 hours of public road driving. The MOOVE database [32] from VEDECOM also contains data from the highway, but the output format is not decided yet. The PEGASUS database [33] contains recorded data from German highways for a large number of kilometres. Based on the challenger concept, known from the PEGASUS methodology [33], logical scenarios for highways with focus on relevant entities are available. The data is stored as parameter distributions and logical scenarios. The PEGASUS database output are parameters which can be varied to reach a wider variety of the parameter space. After that, since variations and adaptations of parameters in OpenSCENARIO and OpenDRIVE can be difficult, the parameters are compiled into the open standards OpenDRIVE and OpenSCENARIO. Finally, one input to the PEGASUS database, but also available separately, the highD/inD dataset [34] from ika contains recorded data from German highways and intersections. The dataset consists of trajectories of recorded traffic participants as well as classifications.

Based on the fact that the StreetWise database offers as output format currently used standards for safety validation of automated driving systems, it looks promising to be utilized for a HEADSTART use case. Its different logical scenario categories offer a wide range of possible applications to various highway pilot functionalities.

Moreover, PEGASUS scenarios are specifically designed for highways. Its challenger approach is a relative approach to step away from solely expert based ideas to find all relevant scenarios, but rather combine expert knowledge with a structural approach. Thus, it seems that the PEGASUS database is also well suited for the highway pilot use case.

Based on UN Regulation on: “Uniform provisions concerning the approval of vehicles with regard to Automated Lane Keeping Systems” [18], relevant scenario categories (logical scenarios) for an important subset of a potential highway pilot functionality can be used. Visual representations of the three categories including the respective parameters can be seen in Figure 21. Using these scenarios (amongst the other test cases described in the document, e.g. an ego vehicle lane change, listed as event in Table 3), basic testing requirements for the different test methods can be derived. These scenarios can be represented by the PEGASUS challenger concept.

Figure 21 is taken from Appendix 3 of Annex 4 in the new UN-Regulation of ALKS [18] and represents only some examples for possible traffic scenarios to be managed by the system. Additional traffic scenarios with multiple

¹ until maximum allowed speed of highway pilot function included in the ego vehicle

vehicles including motorcycles, trucks for obstructions of other traffic participants, stationary objects on the road and also pedestrians (to some extent) are relevant scenario elements which have to be taken into account for a Highway Pilot.

A Highway Pilot including lane change manoeuvre of the ego vehicle will have to cover even more scenarios with approaching vehicles from behind, critical distances respectively the decision of enough gaps in the traffic to perform safe lane changes. This will represent a fourth relevant scenario category for basic test scenarios.

FIGURE 21 SCENARIOS FOR AUTOMATED LANE KEEPING SYSTEMS [18]

3.1.1 Testing of scenarios

To leverage the developed HEADSTART methodology to its full potential, each of the 4 different test methods needs to be applied to the specific use case.

In case of the highway pilot functionality, the current situation, based on the assumption of a typical implementation as described in paragraph 3.1, as well as typical logical scenarios (sub-paragraph 0), leads to the following test method observations:

Virtual testing

Virtually testing a larger number of the described scenarios in chapter 0 is necessary for sake of efficiency. Since for some of the required scenarios, occlusion of relevant traffic participants takes place, a respective sensor model including those effects is required. Additionally, the vehicle dynamics of the ego vehicle must be modelled accordingly, including lateral dynamics required for lane changes. Virtual environments for highways are available, as these are typically easier to either derive from real-world measurements campaigns or synthetically generated.

XiL-based testing

The same principles as described for the Virtual testing also apply for the XiL-based testing. Depending on which element of the simulation framework is replaced by its real-world counterpart, specific requirements vary based on the specific part.

Proving ground testing

Basic requirements for a proving ground in terms of road layout and traffic participants include at least 2 lanes (for a lane change, cut-in/cut-out scenarios) as well as at least two other vehicles (either real or target). Additionally, enough space to execute the scenarios is required, because some scenarios will be executed with high speed this could be a limiting factor to some proving grounds.

Field testing

Field testing for a highway pilot functionality can only be executed on a highway. Either the respective section of a specific highway gets closed for the time of the Field testing or the Field testing is carried out by a credentialed company or institution. If the field test is carried out on a closed highway, only the functions related to the positioning and communication can be tested, as every other layer of the environment is similar to a proving ground (no other real traffic participants available). Special requirements for Field testing the Highway pilot use case in general cannot be derived, apart from the usual restrictions and verifications that need to be executed before the actual deployment of a driving function in real traffic, as it also heavily depends on the actual functionality of the system and ODD.

3.1.2 Evaluation of test results

For the evaluation of test results regarding the Highway pilot use case, a possible structure for evaluation can be based on pre-defined key performance indicators (KPIs). A possible high-level categorization could divide the KPIs into the main sections, driving function-based and scenario-based. The driving function KPIs can include sections for safety, comfort, performance, and efficiency. The scenario KPIs can include sections for metrics (coverage and performance) and success criteria.

The actual KPIs for evaluation need to be defined based on the final chosen scenarios as well as the actual driving function and the respective ODD and OEDR.

3.2 Truck platooning

In this section the HEADSTART methodology is applied to the Truck platooning use case. In the Truck platooning use case, a group of two or more automated cooperative trucks drive together in a line, maintaining a close distance.

Wireless communication is an important aspect in the Truck platooning use case, considering communication between vehicles (tactical and operational layer [35]), as well as communication from the platoon to the outside world (strategic layer [35]). For example, when looking at the operational layer, to enable driving safely at close distances, communication between truck is of vital importance to enable the following truck(s) to respond in time to the preceding truck kinematic behaviour such as (sudden) decelerations. Furthermore, communication can improve longitudinal and lateral string stability of the platoon. Tactical layer communication between vehicles is used to maintain coherence in the platoon (for example sharing information about braking capabilities). On a strategical layer, platoon planning can be performed, which requires communication between the planner and single trucks / truck platoons.

Also, Positioning is a key enabler for the truck platooning functionality or related ADAS functions. The ego-vehicle should know its exact position in the real world (absolute), e.g. on what lane it is currently driving, especially for more advanced truck platooning manoeuvres. Also, its relative position is of importance: is it driving in the centre of the lane, what is the current distance towards a preceding vehicle. This position information must be of high quality, so very accurate, updated in real-time (high sample rates) as not only the ego-truck uses this for its operational control. Via V2X communication, other platoon members will also use this position information for their operational control. To use this external information with a certain level of trust, some (minimal) performance of the position accuracies needs to be specified. The positioning function for a platooning vehicle is often based on fused information from multiple sensor inputs, GNSS, (HD) map data, and extended with communicated vehicle positions received via V2V.

Secure communication is needed such that the trucks in the platoon all trust each other (Confidence: trusted IDs, authenticated) and trust the information they are sharing (integrity of V2V messages) amongst each other. Furthermore, it is needed to protect the communication between the platoon members from external threats. The protection of information and the resilience against external attacks are both part of cybersecurity. Cybersecurity is treated as not use case specific (see paragraph 2.5) and therefore not discussed here in detail.

A crosscheck was made with HEADSTART deliverable D1.3 [14] and D1.4 [4] containing requirements on testability of the KETs. The Truck Platooning use case is particularly useful for testing the KETs Communication and Cybersecurity.

The importance of the HEADSTART KETs Communication (V2X), Positioning and Cybersecurity for the use case Truck platooning were endorsed by external experts during the HEADSTART Truck platooning webinar on May 12, 2020 [36]. Other important enablers mentioned by experts in this webinar are:

- Smart infrastructure: I2V sharing external information to the platoon and also V2I communication for sharing platoon information to external entities. In practice this can be RSU (roadside units) at highways, intersections or some platooning related cloud services. In ENSEMBLE the communication with the infrastructure is part of the service layer/strategic layer. In general, it is part of the V2X communication, but normally relates to informative data at strategic level and sparsely tactical level. V2V data is normally of operational and tactical nature thus of more impact on CAD assessment. I2V / V2I is assumed to be covered in the HEADSTART KET Communication (V2X).
- Human Factors: though Human Factors might be an important enabler for CAD, it is not detailed in the HEADSTART methodology at this point in time

Different levels of automation are envisioned for truck platooning. As a basis for the current discussion an automation level close to real-life deployment is chosen; the first truck in the platoon is driven manually by a human driver, possibly supported by advanced driver assistance systems (ADAS), like Adaptive Cruise Control (ACC) or Autonomous Emergency Braking (AEB). The following trucks have automated longitudinal control, whereas a (safety) driver in each of these trucks is responsible to keep the following truck in its lane. Potentially the lateral control of the following trucks might be supported with an ADAS functionality as well, for example Automated Lane Keeping System (ALKS). This level of automation corresponds to “Platooning Support Function” as described in the ENSEMBLE project [35].

It is expected that the first implementation of truck platooning will be applied on the highway, due to the less complex scenarios (one-way driving direction, controlled entry/exit points, generally good lane markings). For this reason, in the current example use case typical highway conditions are considered, as summarized in Table 4. Typical high level manoeuvres for a truck platoon member could be for example, forming or disengaging a platoon, or platooning in steady-state driving. During these manoeuvres, certain events can occur, such as a cut-in by another vehicle, or a (emergency) braking event in front of the platoon. Detailed examples of truck platooning logical scenarios can be found in [35].

It must be noted that the scenario specifications mentioned in Table 4 are typical for European highways. When considering truck platooning to be applied in other regions, like United States of America or Japan, the ODD (scenario, including communication protocols) will be different. There could be several ways to fill scenario databases, for example based on regions (local, countries, continental, world-wide), or split based on vehicle types and/or automation levels. Although, for example, a world-wide database results in a world-wide applicability, it might prove to be a challenge to incorporate regional differences in a scenario database.

TABLE 4 EXAMPLE SPECIFICATION FOR TRUCK PLATOONING USE CASE SCENARIO

Entry	Value
Area of operation	Open Roads, mixed traffic
Road Type	Highway <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • One-directional traffic, Traffic from other direction is separated by a barrier • Multilane • No intersections • No city limits
Admissible Road Infrastructure	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Roads, tunnels (with limitations), vicinity of highway entry/exit, overpasses, inclines / declines • No construction zone
Dedicated infrastructure	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Clear lane markings in white or yellow (e.g. with reflective paint) • No potholes, obstruction, significant damage on road surface
Speed Range	From 30 km/h to 90 km/h (maximal speed limit may vary per EU country) in acceleration, from 90 km/h to standstill in deceleration

Entry	Value
Environmental Conditions	Included: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Sunny, cloudy, light rain, fog (minimal visibility of X m) • Dry/Damp surface, wet surface • Daylight (daytime), Dark (night-time), Dusk/Dawn Excluded: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Heavy rain, storm, snow, lightning • Slate, icy surface, snow, standing water on road surface
Vehicle Configuration	Trucks Longitudinal control partially automated (accelerate, decelerate, braking up to -3.5m/s^2) Lateral manoeuvres not included (lane change, exit/enter highway)

For scenario based assessment of platooning trucks two possible approaches can be used: assess the platoon as a whole (hence, a system of vehicles) or assess the response of the individual truck within the platoon. In the first approach, various compositions of platoons need to be considered, for example with a different number of trucks, different type of trucks (multi-brand) and a different order of the trucks in a platoon. Performing safety assessment on all possible platoon configurations might in this case become highly complex. Though multi-brand platoon testing increases complexity, it is stated by experts as the preferred option [36].

In the second approach (assessing the individual truck within the platoon) it is important to consider that the individual truck is part of a platoon, and that the individual truck responds to input received by communication as well. In this approach, the assessment should consider the different roles that the truck can have in a platoon (leader, follower, trailing), as its functions will change with the role it has in the platoon.

In the HEADSTART methodology the focus will be on assessing the individual trucks. For complete safety assessment of the platooning system (e.g. type approval) both assessments should be considered, as is also acknowledged by the experts during the HEADSTART Truck platooning webinar [36].

3.2.1 Scenario selection and allocation

As described in section 2.2 the selection of scenarios is divided in two parts; 1) filtering of the relevant logical scenarios and 2) defining the relevant parameter values and combine them into concrete scenarios. Once concrete scenarios are defined, they are allocated to suitable test methods.

As mentioned in section 3.2, it is expected that the first implementations of truck platooning will be applied on highways. Therefore, the focus for this use case will be on typical scenarios on highways (see Table 4 for details). Examples of truck platooning scenarios consider manoeuvres such as joining a platoon, leave a platoon, steady state platooning, emergency braking and platoon gap adaptation [37]. Note that the platoon level, as well as the role of the assessed, individual truck within the platoon, should be considered when describing the scenario and the expected behaviour. A relevant scenario for truck platooning could for example be a new truck joining the platoon from behind, or a vehicle cut-in in front of a following platooning truck.

V2X communication is not yet present in current databases, hence shared digital information should be added to the scenario data. V2X communication considers for example communication between trucks in the platoon (V2V, generally information on a tactical / operational level and hence important in CAD assessment) or communication between truck and infrastructure or cloud (V2I/I2V, generally information strategic / service level).

Current databases do not yet include (real-world) scenario data for platooning. This holds for the behaviour of trucks within the platoon as well as behaviour of other road users interacting with the platoon, especially with small intervehicle distances within a platoon. As an alternative, one can look at typical highway logical scenarios for single trucks, for example lane following, following a preceding vehicle or a vehicle cut-in, where the ego-vehicle is a truck. It is also possible to look at data from following trucks in 'platoon' formation on a highway, though intervehicle distance between the trucks in this situation will generally be larger compared to the truck platooning situation. Since limited truck (platooning) data is available in current databases, it is not trivial to derive relevant parameter distributions for truck platooning scenarios, especially when looking at very platooning specific scenarios. Again, real-world data from – not exactly similar, but – comparable highway scenarios might be used to extract relevant parameter values. An example of a scenario that is relevant for truck platooning, which might be possible to derive from existing data, is an (emergency) braking event in front of the platoon. Parameter distributions of such events (distance at start/end of breaking event, deceleration, etc.) might be obtained from (emergency) braking events of a vehicle in front of a single truck. When using these alternative scenarios that are comparable to truck platooning scenarios, it has to be kept in mind that the scenario might change when going towards actual truck platooning. As a possible solution to the lack of real-world truck platooning data, the HEADSTART methodology allows for an injection of scenarios to the database based on expert knowledge and/or completeness studies.

The behaviour of road users interacting with the platoon might change when road users, and truck platoon (safety) drivers, are getting used to platooning trucks, which might lead to new scenarios or different parameter distributions (for example trucks within a platoon driving at closer distances more often, when (safety) drivers trust the system more and more). By updating the exposure and relevance of scenarios in the database (as explained in [1]) this challenge can be covered.

Current databases (like StreetWise, MOOVE) include no/limited data from trucks as ego vehicle. The PEGASUS database includes trucks as ego vehicle in general and includes trucks in their logical scenario concept. However, there are not specific truck platooning scenarios included yet. It is expected that more data become available from truck platooning applications in real-world settings in the future. The feedback loop in the HEADSTART methodology (as shown in Figure 2) allows for updating scenarios and parameter and its parameter distributions once this data is available.

Once concrete scenarios for truck platooning are defined, they can be allocated to one or more of the four defined test methods: Virtual testing, XiL-based testing, Proving ground testing or Field testing.

3.2.2 Testing of scenarios

As mentioned before, the current focus for the Truck platooning use case will be on highway scenarios (see also Table 4). In this section it will be discussed for each of the 4 test methods, how they are suited for testing of the Truck platooning use case.

Virtual testing

As mentioned previously in this report, Virtual testing is very suitable to test (software) parts of the system under various conditions (scenarios). The V2X communication function can be tested at a logical level, for example when testing the supported interactions of the platooning protocol at a tactical level (e.g. joining, leaving, platoon coherence). If the ego-vehicle platooning protocol expects an input from source truck X, is it "received" as expected? In this example the communication channel is represented as a direct input to the communication

software. The same goes for generating output by the ego-vehicle for logical platoon protocol testing. Another example is testing a Platoon-ACC algorithm; some basic performance evaluation can be tested by changing V2V message update rate as input to the Platoon-ACC algorithm, or adding delays, blocking the input messages, string stability, etc. These examples are more at the operational level, in which Virtual testing can be applied to fine-tune and optimize functionality.

Flexibility in choosing scenario parameter values is high. Hence going towards multiple actors in a scenario, each actor with its own parameter values, is feasible. Since Virtual testing is the safest way of testing functionality (with respect to the other road users, test participants and equipment), it is a suitable way of testing safety critical scenarios (e.g. emergency braking in front of the platoon, or cut-in / cut-through of another vehicle at high velocities and (relatively) small gap). It allows for the evaluation of the (safety) performance of a (sub) function and for finetuning these functions.

A major drawback of Virtual testing is that the results and possibilities depend heavily on the accuracy of the models used. This holds for modelling of components, sensors, kinematics as well as environmental conditions. Creation and validation of detailed models is expensive, and however much effort is being spent on them, they remain a modelled representation of reality.

XiL-based testing

In XiL-based testing, hardware parts are included in a virtual environment. In this way, the included hardware can be tested as a whole, including delays, sensor noise, hardware performance limitations (CPU power, memory, buffer, processing times) etc. This is very relevant for testing the communication functionality of the truck platoon system. Previously, in the Virtual testing section, an example with some logical platooning interactions (message from A is received by B) was used. By adding the communication hardware, the wireless channel becomes part of the system-under-test. This allows for additional physical V2X testing with a more realistic communication channel behaviour (bounded channel, interference, delays, etc.) and also with the real-life performance offered by the communication devices. Multiple functions on multiple hardware platforms can be tested in an integrated way. This will also 'smoothen' the transition of the platooning application from an XiL environment to the actual vehicle deployment.

A drawback of XiL-based testing is that hardware parts are commonly tested in 'ideal' conditions. For example, when looking at the communication unit example, if the radio channel in the XiL-based setting is just over the air with the devices close to each other, the complete V2X communication systems is used, however under non-realistic conditions for the communication channel without disturbances. For this the antennas need to be deployed on the actual vehicle and tested in dynamic conditions like possible in Proving ground testing.

Proving ground testing

Proving ground tests are relevant for testing the full vehicle and platoon system, in close to real-world conditions. The full V2X communication system can be tested under real driving conditions, including sub-optimal antenna locations and obstructed line-of-sight (by ego-vehicle, other platooning vehicles), changing line-of-sight conditions because of road layout, corners. V2X range limitations can occur on the proving ground. The V2V communication, which is a safety-critical part of the platooning application, can be tested in a controlled environment, and the performance can be evaluated. Furthermore, Proving ground testing can be used to validate vehicle dynamics models and sensor models used in Virtual testing or XiL-based testing. It is a first possibility to test differences between XiL towards real vehicle deployment with real V2V interactions under real driving conditions. Compared to Field testing, Proving ground tests provide a more controlled environment, safer testing conditions (system performance is often to be tested). Moreover, it can be used to prove some minimal safety performance of the ADAS/platooning application under reproducible conditions.

In highway scenarios, the (initial) velocity of the participating vehicles (vehicle under test and other actors) is relatively high (up to 80-100 km/h). Also, the platoon itself, including multiple trucks, is covering more space compared to single vehicles. For these reasons, in Proving ground testing, a significant stretch of highway(-like) surface has to be available with relatively large corner radii to enable the trucks to keep cruising speed. Moreover, safe testing at these velocities is challenging, as is timing of manoeuvres and reproducibility for scenarios with multiple actors. The availability of infrastructural objects, such as gantries, bridges and tunnels (which can have a significant influence on V2X and GNSS reception), or inclines/declines of the road (which will influence the braking / acceleration performance of the trucks) as well as road curvatures are limited and hence testing these on a proving ground is challenging or even impossible.

Field testing

Field testing provides the most realistic environment to test the performance of the complete truck platoon system. Infrastructural elements that are not commonly available on proving grounds (gantries, tunnels, as mentioned above) are available for Field testing, by testing for example on public highways. It has to be noted that highways are to be closed for other traffic when testing, and/or it might be necessary to arrange exemptions to allow the automated vehicles to drive on the road. Depending on the exact scenario(s) that are to be tested, the stretch of (closed) highway should be sufficiently long and should contain the required infrastructural elements. Generally, a certain level of performance and safety has to be shown via Proving ground testing before Field testing is allowed.

3.2.3 Evaluation of test results

As mentioned in section 3.2, the HEADSTART methodology will focus on assessing the individual trucks. Tests are to be assessed with metrics regardless if the test is performed by Virtual testing, XiL-based, Proving ground testing or Field testing. Typical metrics for the Truck platooning use case are for example:

- V2X Communication: is the information sent by the truck correct and complete, is the information sent by other trucks correctly received (do we have operational communication channel(s)), can we exchange the messages, can we interpret the messages, are the message update rates as expected (frequency, timing) for basic communication functions. Note that these evaluations can be done on an individual truck as well as on a complete platoon.
- Operational: does the platoon leader correctly adapt speed at inclines/declines according to the minimal performing truck in platoon, is the platoon leader role correctly transferred in case of a platoon split or merge. Again, such evaluations can be done on single truck as well as a full platoon.
- Safety: safe (and expected) behaviour in case of GPS loss / packet loss / communication loss, unauthorized / untrusted access etc.

3.3 Traffic jam chauffeur

In this section the HEADSTART methodology is applied to the Traffic jam chauffeur use case.

Most drivers find traffic jams irritating and annoying. They usually occur unexpectedly. The additional time that they consume on the way to work, to shopping, to visit friends, or on vacation causes a great deal of dissatisfaction, stress, and anger.

Due to their monotony and low workload, traffic jams increase fatigue and reduce attention and concentration. Hence, the probability of minor slips and lapses is increased. Therefore, traffic jams are the kind of situations where a high degree of automation could confer a great deal of benefit on customers when a situation cannot be avoided.

Moreover, the relatively simple situations and low velocities of a usual traffic jam means that a high degree of automation can be expected in the near future.

The traffic jam chauffeur functionality can be activated in case of a traffic jam scenario. It detects a slow driving vehicle in front and then handles the vehicle both longitudinally and laterally. The driver must deliberately activate the system but does not have to monitor the system constantly. The driver can at all times override or switch off the system. In case of a takeover request to the driver from the system, the driver has sufficient time reserved to orientate themselves and take over the driving task. In case the driver does not take over, the system will aim to go to a minimised risk condition, i.e. bring the vehicle to a safe stop.

Conditional automated driving in traffic jams up to 60 km/h on motorways and motorway similar roads was recently (June 2020) adopted via a new UN Regulation on Automated Lane Keeping [18]. It detects slow driving vehicle in front and at the side and then drives the vehicle both longitudinal and lateral. Later version of this functionality might include a lane change functionality.

The abovementioned UN regulation for Automated Lane Keeping provides a regulatory context that is relevant for part of the Traffic Jam Chauffeur functionality. As a use case description usually encompasses many different reference implementations, also many different descriptions of the Operational Design Domain (ODD) belonging to a Traffic jam chauffeur use case exist. The UN Regulation WP.29/2020/81 therefore does not refer to one of these descriptions and defines a complete set of requirements for a traffic jam chauffeur functionality (ALKS: Automated Lane Keeping System). The following table describes one possible ODD:

TABLE 5 EXAMPLE SPECIFICATION FOR TRAFFIC JAM CHAUFFEUR USE CASE SCENARIO

Entry	Value
Area of operation	Open Roads, mixed traffic
Road Type	Highway, urban <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Two-directional traffic • Multilane • Intersections • No city limits
Admissible Road Infrastructure	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Roads, tunnels, vicinity of highway entry/exit, overpasses, inclines / declines • Construction zone

Entry	Value
Dedicated infrastructure	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Clear lane markings in white or yellow (e.g. with reflective paint) • No potholes, obstruction, significant damage on road surface
Speed Range	From 30 km/h to 60 km/h (maximal speed limit may vary per EU country)
Environmental Conditions	<p>Included:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Sunny, cloudy, light rain, fog (minimal visibility of X m) • Dry/Damp surface, wet surface • Daylight (daytime), Dark (nighttime), Dusk/Dawn <p>Excluded:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Heavy rain, storm, snow, lightning • Slate, icy surface, snow, standing water on road surface
Vehicle Configuration	Passenger cars with a maximum gross vehicle mass up to 3500 kg

A crosscheck was made with HEADSTART deliverable D1.3 [14] and D1.4 [4] containing requirements on testability of the KETs. The Traffic jam chauffeur use case is particularly useful for testing the KETs Communication and Positioning.

Communication (V2X) could be used to provide to the function information about traffic situation in order to provide extra information to the automated driving system for being taken into consideration in the decision making algorithms and improve its performance.

Positioning should be used to limit functions to safe scenarios (such as highway driving) that conform to predetermined areas of application. Moreover, map data could also be useful to improve system availability. If the complexity of the system under review grows in highly automated functions, the inclusion of GPS positioning data and highly accurate mapping data is very likely to become necessary to provide the redundancy demanded by the number and curvature of lane markings or to predict the driving path of the vehicle when (temporarily) losing the lane marking detection. This information plays a decisive role in applying functions to urban scenarios in particular. Comparisons with landmarks captured above and beyond the road surface, such as bridge pillars or traffic signs, are a logical extension of such systems.

3.3.1 Scenario selection and allocation

The selection of scenarios for the Traffic jam chauffeur use case seems to be quite similar to the selection of scenarios for the Highway pilot use case with a more limited ODD in terms of vehicle speeds and with the possibility for simplifications and to skip some scenarios for basic systems like ALKS because of the limited functionality of the system defined in a limited ODD. This, on the one hand, narrows down the parameter space, but, on the other hand, requires a deeper and more detailed look into low speed traffic participant interaction. Even pedestrians on the open road can become more relevant or likely, since in traffic jams, in terms of highways unusual situations can occur. Parked vehicles or trucks on the side of the road are a common phenomenon of traffic jams.

Looking into traffic jam scenarios in general by evaluating occurring problems and challenges in today's traffic jams, the databases of PEGASUS, StreetWise and MOOVE seem to be suitable. All have traffic jams somehow included in their scenario concepts. Especially, end of traffic jam seems to be a widely used logical scenario. However, in PEGASUS this is included in the challenger approach itself. Especially, the interaction within the traffic jam can be described by either different challenger logical scenarios of PEGASUS with low speeds, but also with logical scenarios like follow or cut-in.

When taking a more detailed look into traffic jams, it seems to be covered by existing databases. Nevertheless, the trade-off between taking only relevant situations and scenarios into account and not missing scenarios is still a problem for that specific use case.

The new UN Regulation for ALKS [18] covers in the Annex 5 of the Regulation an entire set of relevant scenarios needed for an evaluation of a basic functionality of a traffic jam chauffeur system.

PEGASUS, StreetWise and MOOVE can provide a wide variety of scenarios for the use case traffic jam, especially on highways. These additional scenarios and scenario parameter variations could also help varying the test cases in the approval process. The possibility of a free variation of parameters and test scenarios within the mandatory requirements for a system is a new approach in this new UN Regulation for ALKS to cover more possible scenarios and not limit the approval process to some very limited test cases. The intention is to give the approval process more flexibility to assess a system performance and to come closer to the real system performance in real traffic. Thus, the methodology of HEADSTART can be applied by also utilizing the stated databases.

3.3.2 Testing of scenarios

In this section it will be discussed for the four different methods of testing, how they are suited for the use case Traffic jam chauffeur with respect to testing of scenarios. For this use case, first requirements for testing of specific scenarios have been established in the aforementioned UN Regulation concerning the approval of vehicles with regard to Automated Lane Keeping Systems (ALKS). Since this UN Regulation limits the operational speed to 60 km/h maximum and is intended for passenger cars only, this can be referred to the HEADSTART use case Traffic jam chauffeur.

The annex 5 of the UNECE document defines six different tests with the purpose to verify the technical requirements on the system. The tests are intended to be performed mainly on proving grounds, so this can be referred to the method of Proving ground testing. It is intended that a Technical Service ensures that the ALKS is subject to the tests outlined in the document. Pass-/Fail-Criteria for the tests are derived from the technical requirements of the regulation. The requirements are designed in a way that they allow for a combination of parameters in which the system is designed to work (e.g. operating speed range, operating longitudinal acceleration range, safety distances, etc.). The test specifications in the document are meant to be a minimum set of tests.

Proving ground testing

The first test is intended to examine that the traffic jam chauffeur does not leave its travel lane and maintains a stable position inside its lane across different speeds and curvatures within the system boundaries. The test shall be performed over duration of at least 5 minutes and with different lead/target vehicles/road users in front of the test vehicle.

The second described test is designed to test that the traffic jam chauffeur avoids a collision with a stationary vehicle, road user or fully or partially blocked lane by another object up to the maximum design speed of the system. The collision avoidance test shall be executed with a passenger car, a powered two-wheeler and a pedestrian target as well as with a target/obstacle partially or fully blocking the lane. The test is also intended to be performed on a curved road section.

The third test mentioned in the document focuses on the system's ability to maintain and restore a defined distance to a vehicle in front and to avoid a collision with a lead vehicle, if this decelerates up to its maximum deceleration. The test shall be performed over the entire speed range of the system (constant and varying lead velocities) and for a passenger car as well as a powered two-wheeler as a lead target. The test shall be performed on straight and curved road sections as well as for different lateral positions of the lead vehicle in the lane.

The fourth test shall demonstrate that the traffic jam chauffeur is capable of avoiding a collision with a vehicle cutting into the lane of the traffic jam chauffeur vehicle up to a certain criticality. In this special situation it is respected that not all situations induced by the other traffic can be solved by the ALKS vehicle with a fully crash avoidance.

The fifth test shall demonstrate that the traffic jam chauffeur is also capable of avoiding a collision with a stationary vehicle, road user or blocked lane that becomes visible after a preceding vehicle avoided a collision by an evasive manoeuvre (for example cut-out manoeuvre). The test shall be executed with a passenger car, a powered two-wheeler and a pedestrian target as well as with single and multiple consecutive targets/obstacles blocking the lane.

The last test is intended to examine the field of view of the system. The detection of another road user within the forward detection area as well as a vehicle beside within the lateral detection area shall be tested.

Additionally, some standard tests for the verification of basic system functionalities as activation, deactivation and overriding possibilities for the driver, warnings and displays, driver monitoring, transition demand and activation of a Minimum Risk Manoeuvre are conducted or comprehended by the Technical Service.

Virtual testing

The method of Virtual testing additionally to the above described proving ground tests of UN Regulation Annex 5 is outlined in the UN Regulation [18] as well by focusing on performance models of the ALKS for guidance on traffic disturbance critical scenarios (see Annex 4 of the UN Regulation). The proposed simulation focuses on conditions under which the ALKS shall avoid a collision following an attentive human driver performance model and related parameters in traffic critical disturbance scenarios. As mentioned for other use cases, Virtual testing is able to test mainly software parts of the system by manipulating various conditions and circumstances, which makes this method very flexible and suitable for a broad range of scenario parameter, also for the use case Traffic jam chauffeur.

XiL-based testing

XiL-based testing is not included in the UN Regulation document. Since this method is focusing on primarily testing hardware parts in a virtual environment, it is suitable to test the sensor models and other hardware components of the traffic jam chauffeur in a safe and controllable (virtual) environment. Especially vehicle guidance based on the HEADSTART KETs input can be tested for this use case by XiL-based test methods. However, since the degrees of realism for the tested components might vary depending on the simulated elements, additional real-world testing might be necessary to interpret the results validly.

Field testing

Therefore, Field testing is an additional important aspect of a holistic testing strategy, especially with respect to issues related to mixed traffic, which at first sight will be the case for the application of the use case traffic jam chauffeur in the near future. For a first impression and to gain first insights into the functionality, also the UN Regulation describes real-world testing as one additional test component. The document defines, that the Technical Service shall conduct or witness the assessment of the system in a fault-free condition and in the presence of real traffic. The purpose of this test is to support the Technical Service in understanding the functionality of the system in its operating environment and to complement the assessment primarily performed

on proving grounds. To minimize criticality in a relatively uncontrolled environment, it is recommended that the real-world test is undertaken only once the system has passed all of the other tests.

3.3.3 Evaluation of test results

The pass/fail criteria to assess the test results are laid down in the requirements section of the new UN Regulation. The pass/fail criteria described in the requirement section are derived from necessities for road safety and traffic flow and shall be fulfilled independently of the test method. Proving ground testing, Virtual testing, XiL-based testing and Field testing should not include or introduce new pass/fail criteria. The purpose of the different test methods is only to prove, that the system fulfils all requirements of the main regulation text.

Typical pass/fail criteria in the new UN Regulation [18] are:

- The activated system shall keep the vehicle inside its lane of travel and ensure that the vehicle does not cross any lane marking. The system shall aim to keep the vehicle in a stable lateral position inside the lane of travel to avoid confusing other road users.
- The activated system shall perform the dynamic driving task, shall manage all situations including failures and shall be free of unreasonable risks for the vehicle occupants or any other road users.
- The activated system shall not cause any collisions that are reasonably foreseeable and preventable. If a collision can be safely avoided without causing another one, it shall be avoided. When the vehicle is involved in a detectable collision, the vehicle shall be brought to a standstill.
- The activated system shall comply with traffic rules relating to the dynamic driving task in the country of operation.
- The activated system shall exercise control over systems required to support the driver in resuming manual control at any time (e.g. demist, windscreen wipers and lights).
- The activated system shall recognise all situations in which it needs to transfer the control back to the driver. A transition demand to transfer the dynamic driving task back to the driver shall not endanger the safety of the vehicle occupants or other road users.
- Types of situations in which the vehicle will generate a transition demand to the driver shall be declared by the vehicle manufacturer and included in the documentation package required in Annex 4 of the Regulation.
- The initiation of the transition demand shall be such that sufficient time is provided for a safe transition to manual driving.
- If the driver fails to resume control of the dynamic driving task during the transition phase, the system shall perform a minimum risk manoeuvre. During a minimum risk manoeuvre, the system shall minimise risks to safety of the vehicle occupants and other road users.
- The system shall perform self-checks to detect the occurrence of failures and to confirm system performance at all times (e.g. after vehicle starts the system has at least once detected an object at the same or a higher distance than that declared as detection range).
- The effectiveness of the system shall not be adversely affected by magnetic or electrical fields.
- The manufacturer shall take measures to guard against reasonably foreseeable misuse by the driver and tampering of the system.
- When the system can no longer meet the requirements of this Regulation, it shall not be possible to activate the system. The manufacturer shall declare and implement a process to manage the safety and continued compliance of the ALKS system over lifetime.

4 Testing feasibility

In this chapter some particular observations are described based on experiences by various partners and consultation of experts during workshops and in the HEADSTART webinar week [36]. This is not a complete analysis but intended to highlight some of the challenges that are expected to be encountered when the HEADSTART methodology will be applied in WP3 and WP4. The different methods have been explored from different angles to cover different areas of attention.

For Field testing the focus was on experience and lessons learned by type approval authority. The relevance of Virtual testing is briefly described for each HEADSTART use case. Different implementations of XiL-based testing are shortly outlined with its advantages and disadvantages. In the last section the feasibility of Proving ground testing is discussed.

4.1 Field testing

In this paragraph, the lessons learned from the relevant field operational trials in the Netherlands are shared. Different trials have been conducted, with an emphasis on automated shuttles and car- and truck platooning. In line with the use cases of HEADSTART, the lessons learned from the truck platooning trials will be explained below.

In general, admittance testing:

- For risk analysis, the vehicles and the operational domain are always assessed together.
- Vehicles must be as much as possible in line with type approval regulations and where this is not possible, a risk analysis based on the ISO26262 or SOTIF is required.
- Applicants lack electromagnetic compatibility (EMC) knowledge and awareness. No EMC resulted in some malfunctions or errors during testing.
- An RDW accredited test house explained: “Because there are no pass / fail criteria for autonomous systems, for example ADAS and / or automated vehicles, these systems can be switched off during the EMC tests”. So even when EMC tests are conducted, a vehicle authority needs to be aware what is tested.
- Regular admission does not pay attention to software obsolescence. By requiring good risk analyses, updates are forced.

In general, what we saw during the trials:

- Sensitivity of common sensors for rain is very large.
- Within the same software version, sometimes parameters were changed resulting in behavioral changes.
- Aging and misplacement (too hot or poorly ventilated) of electronics components.
- We saw automated systems that started braking after detection within 300 to 500 ms. We also saw human response time of 1,5 – 2 seconds. This will have an impact on new legislation for braking.

For platooning:

- It is time consuming to reconnect after other traffic cut into a platoon.
- The effectiveness of the truck platooning concept is reduced when there are a large number of on- and off-ramps close together.
- Visibility: Putting stripes or other visual markings on the trucks would help identify them as a platoon.
- Lane changing: for platoons to change lanes as a “team” is a relatively swift maneuver, often taking less than 10 seconds. When they decouple to change lanes individually it takes longer, due to the presence of other traffic.
- On- and off-ramps are the most challenging traffic situations, particularly when merging with single trucks.

On drivers:

- Drivers response time is slower in more situations than we had assumed. Driver State Monitoring is needed.
- Lateral support provides ease for the driver.
- The lead truck driver needs to be aware of the full length of the platoon.
- The lead truck driver mainly tends to look ahead, watching out for potential problems.
- Radio communication is important in informing drivers of following trucks; video communication is for verification.
- Experienced truck drivers are important. They know the eventualities and can respond accordingly.

For the truck platoon challenge in 2016 [38] a code of practice was made for the applicants to highlight desired behavior on Dutch roads during the trials. Because this could not be covered in the exemption, we asked the drivers to voluntarily abide this code of practice. The practice contained rules regarding forming and maintaining the platoon, following, overtaking, merging, unplanned stops and diversions.

4.2 Virtual testing

Based on the detailed use case descriptions of chapter 3, (minimum) requirements for Virtual testing should be derived in this paragraph. Afterward, statements about the general testing feasibility regarding Virtual testing can be made for each specific use case.

In Table 6 an overview of the requirements for the different blocks of the model-based testing approach, displayed in Figure 8, can be seen. The different categories reflect the necessary and relevant blocks for a simulation framework. For the driving function, this means information about tactical manoeuvres, the ODD and the OEDR. Additionally, appropriate failure modes and the actual function code must be provided as a minimum. For the sensors, the field of view as well as the sensor position on the ego vehicle is required. Additional fidelity for the sensor models can be provided if the necessary information is provided. Regarding vehicle dynamics, the mass as well as the dimensions of the ego vehicle are minimum requirements for testing feasibility. Additionally, measurement requirements for model verification are stated in Table 6. Lastly, the virtual environment, static as well as dynamic, needs to be provided or generated based on respective input.

For the defined use cases in the HEADSTART project, the following process is used to derive the testing feasibility in terms of Virtual testing:

- Based on the driving function (and the respective definition of the ODD and OEDR) the necessary elements from the environment, which the driving function needs to fulfil the defined functional requirements (and therefore the dynamic driving task) are derived.
- Using this information, the fidelity and the required elements in the virtual environment are defined.
- Based on that, the necessary fidelity and requirements for the sensor models can be derived.
- Analysing the potential manoeuvres of the driving function in the different defined logical scenarios, the necessary fidelity of the vehicle dynamics model can be derived.

Highway pilot use case

For the Highway pilot use case, described in paragraph 3.1, this means the following:

Usually (details depend on the actual driving function) a function based in the Highway pilot use case, will be using camera, radar and potentially LiDAR technology for detecting other traffic participants as well as lane markings and drivable space. Additionally, GPS is used as well as an underlying HD-map. For the virtual environment, this means that the road network (including lanes with width and markings, but also undulations and banking), ideally with the correct (or a realistic) geo-reference (for easier cross-validation with potential Field or Proving ground tests), needs to be defined. If necessary, for the function, traffic signs need to be included as well. For the sensor models, this means that occlusions need to be considered for the traffic participants. Regarding the vehicle dynamics model, lateral and longitudinal dynamics need to be considered.

Truck platooning use case

For the Truck platooning use case, described in paragraph 3.2, this means the following:

For the Truck platooning use case, V2X communication is an important focus of the testing. Therefore, an environment, which could model the realistic effects of such communication needs to be considered. Otherwise, only a low-fidelity functional test could be executed using Virtual testing. For the vehicle dynamics, longitudinal dynamics are important, depending on the pre-defined KPIs (e.g. including potential benefits of platooning use cases like a reduction of fuel consumption) it may be necessary to model them with high fidelity to be able to make a sufficiently precise statement about the benefits of this use case.

Traffic jam chauffeur use case

For the Traffic jam chauffeur use case, described in paragraph 3.3, this means the following:

The situation of the Traffic jam chauffeur use case is similar to the Highway pilot use case, in the sense that the required virtual environment is more or less equal (once again, depending on the actual function). Although the velocities of the ego vehicle in the Traffic jam chauffeur use case are much lower than in the Highway pilot use case, the fidelity of the vehicle dynamics model is the same to accurately model necessary braking manoeuvres (in critical scenarios).

TABLE 6 OVERVIEW OF MODEL-BASED TESTING APPROACH AND SUB-ELEMENTS

CAD function
Tactical manoeuvres
ODD elements
OEDR
Failure Modes
CAD function as code (for Software-in-the-Loop/Model-in-the-Loop) and on target hardware (ECU) (for Hardware-in-the-Loop)
Sensors
Sensor setup (field of view from all the sensors + sensor position on VUT)
Object-list based feedback from the driven scenarios of the VUT
GPS data from VUT during scenario (for KET Positioning)
For probabilistic sensor models: statistical failure rates
For physical sensor models: detailed knowledge of the respective sensor properties
Vehicle dynamics
Mass / dimensions / Centre of gravity/ (Moment of inertia for z-axis) of VUT
Minimal vehicle dynamics measurements: Exact position (with Differential-GPS) and orientation
Vehicle dynamics measurements from scenarios (and/or basic scenarios) including lateral & longitudinal acceleration, steering wheel angle, pedal positions
VUT on test bench (for Vehicle-in-the-Loop)
Virtual environment – Static
OpenDRIVE description for the scenario (including potential special conditions on Proving ground)
Virtual environment – Dynamic
OpenSCENARIO description (of the scenario to be tested via Proving ground and/or Virtual testing)

4.3 XiL-based testing

As mentioned in 2.3.3, X-in-the-Loop (XiL) based testing is a type of testing combining real and virtual elements of both Connected and Automated Vehicle (CAV) and its environment. The amount of virtual and real elements can vary from having just a single hardware unit of the CAV in a virtual environment to having several real participants on a proving ground and simulating just minor elements of the CAV. Overall, XiL-based testing is a good compromise between Proving ground testing that is very realistic and Virtual testing that allows to test a higher number of scenarios.

XiL-based testing allows critical (hardware and software) parts of the system to be tested in a controlled and repeatable environment with limited effort. Despite the fact that the creation and validation of the XiL setup is time consuming, XiL-based testing allows the execution of a large set of test cases. Another drawback of XiL-based testing is that (hardware and software) parts are commonly tested in 'ideal' conditions.

XiL-based testing is not yet included in the UN Regulation, since this method is focusing on primarily testing hardware parts in a virtual environment and the degrees of realism for the tested components might vary depending on the simulated elements. For that reason, additional real-world testing (Proving ground and/or Field testing) might be necessary to interpret the results validly.

For consumer testing the XiL-based version with the full vehicle in the loop is of special interest as this will contain most of the parts of the vehicles and would be visually more credible to consumers. These setups could for example be used to test highway pilot or traffic jam chauffeur functionalities in complex and dangerous situations on a proving ground. Test cases with many actors where the vehicle under test should handle a dangerous situation could be tested with virtual participants to avoid that physical collisions happen. But also, a vehicle under test placed in a fully virtual environment to allow easy changes of environment in order to see the difference in system behaviour would allow for much more test cases compared to Proving ground testing. The interaction between driver and CAV is out of scope for the HEADSTART project, but also there XiL-based testing could play an important role. With XiL-based testing like a driving simulator the driver interaction could be evaluated in a controlled and non-dangerous way in many variations, independent of outdoor environment.

Using communication hardware in a virtual environment allows the wireless channel to become part of the system-under-test, which allows physical V2X testing with a more realistic communication channel behaviour (bounded channel, interference, delays, etc.). Especially for the Truck platooning use case this is relevant as V2X communication is an essential part of this cooperative driving feature. XiL-based testing also allows multiple functions on multiple hardware platforms (representing multiple trucks) to be tested in an integrated way.

A drawback of XiL-based testing is that hardware parts are commonly tested in 'ideal' conditions. For example, a XiL setup with communication devices close to each other do not fully represent a realistic environment with disturbances, such as high buildings. To include these disturbances the antennas would need to be deployed on the actual vehicle and tested in dynamic conditions like possible in Proving ground or Field testing.

Due to the large variety of possible XiL set-ups with combinations of arbitrary components in different tools and platforms a common framework is necessary. A common format is needed to be able to use different XiL-based setups, but also to easily link with the other testing methods (Virtual and Proving ground testing) and ensure the interchangeability of the test case definitions and the results. Within the HEADSTART project different possible solutions were analysed and it turned out that the ASAM Open Simulation Interface (OSI) is a suitable candidate for this (see D2.1 [1] and D2.2 [3]).

4.4 Proving ground testing

To enable Proving ground testing for certain use cases, several (minimum) requirements have to be fulfilled. Since the different use cases require different test vehicles, test speeds, test equipment, infrastructure elements, etc., different requirements for each use case should be taken into account. Therefore, this paragraph describes the results of a feasibility assessment of Proving ground testing for each use case selected by HEADSTART individually, highlighting some of the use case particular aspects.

Highway pilot use case

General requirements for the use case Highway pilot can be split into the categories road infrastructure and test equipment. Requirements for road infrastructure include at least a two-lane track with road markings according to UNECE Regulation 130. Road length strongly depends on the possibilities of existing proving grounds, a minimum of 2 km straight line or an appropriate circuit is recommended.

Dummy objects can be for example 3D-car targets that are well described in ISO/DIS 19206-3 [39], or 3D-motorcycle targets described in the upcoming ISO/DIS WD 19206-5 (Road vehicles — Test devices for target vehicles, vulnerable road users and other objects, for assessment of active safety functions — Part 5: Requirements for Powered Two-Wheeler targets).

Robotic target carrier platforms used for bigger objects as 3D-car targets can actually speed up to 100 km/h, platforms used for smaller objects like powered two wheelers up to 80 km/h, therefore the intended maximum speed of 130 km/h cannot be covered.

Up to 5 robotic platforms can be used in parallel for the time being, to ensure interoperability between different manufacturers. A standardized protocol is in development and described in ISO/WD TS 22133-1 [40].

Truck platooning use case

Minimum requirements for the use case Truck platooning regarding road infrastructure are the same as for the use case Highway pilot, where track length might be even more demanding due to the length of the truck platoon itself.

Test equipment can be used in different ways: One option would include a robotic platform as part of the platoon (leading or trailing vehicle). An appropriate communication device must be equipped to the platform. Realistic, crashable targets can be attached (e.g. rear end of a truck). Actual state-of-the-art platforms can speed up to 100 km/h and decelerate up to 6 m/s^2 , exceeding the requirements depicted in paragraph 3.2. The second option represents objects outside of the platoon. This can be static objects like 3D-car targets (according to in ISO/DIS 19206-3 [39]) at the end of a traffic jam, roadside furniture, or moving objects used for breaking or cut-in or cut-out scenarios. Both options can be combined to increase the complexity of the scenario.

No physical 3D-targets are available representing a truck and/or trailer, which makes it challenging to test safety critical situations related to detection of an actual truck or trailer.

Since all existing robotic platforms rely on communication to a central control unit, responsible for controlling the path and triggering certain actions, communication range is a critical issue. Single path communication is actually possible up to 1 km, for bigger distances mesh-systems have to be introduced.

Traffic jam chauffeur use case

For the use case Traffic jam chauffeur, first requirements for testing have been established in a new UN Regulation concerning the approval of vehicles with regard to Automated Lane Keeping Systems (ALKS) [18]. The Annex 5 of the UN document defines at least six different tests scenarios as described in 3.3.1. with different test cases with the purpose to verify the technical requirements on the system, which are intended to be performed on proving grounds. Additionally, in verification tests like activation and deactivation possibilities, driver monitoring,

transition procedure and Minimum Risk Manoeuvre, the manufacturer can demonstrate the basic functionalities of the system to the Technical Service in an appropriate manner. In addition to the above-mentioned test cases the Technical Service can perform proving ground test for special situations like different weather or road surfaces conditions and can also perform real world driving tests with the activated system. It is intended that a Technical Service ensures that the system is subject to the tests outlined in the document.

Since the UN regulation defines that the traffic jam chauffeur should be activated only under certain conditions on roads equipped with a physical separation that divides the traffic moving in opposite directions and prevent cross traffic, the proving ground composition must fit to this requirement. To perform the defined tests under valid conditions, the tests should be performed on a proving ground that allows the usual activation and performance of the system. Therefore, all ODD specific system requirements (weather, traffic, etc.) have to be taken into account. If system modifications are required in order to allow testing on a proving ground, this should not have an effect on the test results and the performance of the system.

Furthermore, in a first step, the operational speed for this use case will be limited to 60 km/h maximum. Therefore, the proving ground composition must be suitable for a speed range of at least between 0 and 60 km/h. Since the system mainly keeps the vehicle within its lane, certain lane markings are an important prerequisite. A test to demonstrate that the system does not leave its lane and maintains a stable position inside its lane shall be executed with a test duration of at least 5 minutes. Therefore, the respective proving ground needs to have a suitable length (minimum 5 km) or include a circuit course. Furthermore, since some tests are considering lane change manoeuvres, the test track must include at least two marked lanes. The defined tests include several test targets. The detection of a vehicle (category M or N), a powered-two-wheeler/motorcycle as well as a pedestrian shall be tested using targets applicable to the sensor system of the traffic jam chauffeur (artificial targets according to ISO 19206-3:2018, ISO CD 19206-5, ISO 19206-2:2018). For some tests also real vehicles shall be included. Furthermore, the avoidance of a collision with a stationary vehicle, road users and other obstacles/targets partially or fully blocking the lane shall be tested. The required equipment needs to be available on the proving ground to perform the tests.

If the proving ground compositions as well as the test scenarios fulfil the described requirements, Proving ground testing for the use case Traffic jam chauffeur is highly feasible and recommended. Especially critical scenarios can be tested in a safe and controlled environment with appropriate expenditure and effort.

5 Conclusions

This report describes the scenario-based HEADSTART safety assessment methodology for Connected and Automated Vehicles (CAVs) in short, based on the earlier HEADSTART deliverables D2.1 [1] and D2.2 [3]. Special attention is given to the inclusion of HEADSTART Key Enabling Technologies (KETs): Communication (V2X) and Positioning as part of the method. It was identified that the 3rd HEADSTART KET, Cybersecurity, needs to be treated in a different way due to its different nature, this it is discussed in a separate section. Some implications that could rise from type approval side for the safety assessment are described, with special attention to the admittance and exemptions of CAVs for testing, demonstration or approval activities. Besides type approval authorities also the other two HEADSART key user groups, OEMs & Tier1s and consumer testing, have been taken into account.

Furthermore, the first steps of applying the HEADSTART methodology to the use cases selected by HEADSTART (Highway pilot, Truck platooning & Traffic jam chauffeur) is described. Special attention is payed to the HEADSTART KETs Communication (V2X) and Positioning, resulting in specific challenges related to the HEADSTART use cases when applying the HEADSTART method. An example is the inclusion of assessing Communication (V2X), which is a key-stone for the truck platooning use case. For each of the HEADSTART use cases the 3 main parts of the HEADSTART method: “Scenario selection and allocation”, “Testing of scenarios” and “Evaluation of test results” are set out and some use case specific observations are mentioned. The traffic jam chauffeur use case is being looked at considering in particular the upcoming regulatory requirements in relation to the HEADSTART methodology and its testing methods.

For each of the four HEADSTART test methods (Field, Virtual, XiL-based and Proving ground testing) some implications are touched upon considering the HEADSTART use cases or methodology in general. For example, the requirements on proving ground testing of the use case Truck platooning due to the sheer size and manoeuvrability of a platoon and its individual trucks are mentioned, but also the linked communication requirements. Various lessons-learned from type approval authority information are discussed for field testing. A common format is needed to easily link the different HEADSTART testing methods (Field, Virtual, XiL-based and Proving ground testing) and ensure the interchangeability of the test case definitions and the results.

The activities of HEADSTART T2.4 “*Definition of methodology for the targeted use cases*” itself and the reported findings in this document, as well as the deliverable D2.1 and D2.2, are used in HEADSTART WP3 “*Procedures, environments and tools*” to further detail the HEADSTART methodology with procedures and tools. In WP4 “*Application and demonstration*” the HEADSTART methodology including these procedures and tools will be applied and demonstrated through the different HEADSTART use cases to show its potential.

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